

Commons and Policy: Compilation of Inputs and Reflections IASC Europe and CIS Colloquium Series 2022

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hosted by the Institute of Social Anthropology, University of Bern, Switzerland

Organisation: Tobias Haller and Ilkhom Soliev,
coordinators of the Regional Chapter for Europe and CIS,
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IASC Europe and CIS Colloquium Series on Commons and Policy

Organised by Tobias Haller and Ilkhom Soliev (Regional Coordination Team, IASC Europe and CIS)

Between March and May 2022, IASC Europe & CIS in collaboration with the Institute of Social Anthropology hosted a colloquium series featuring presentations by international speakers. Thematically, the presentations within the series were dedicated to policy issues related to the commons and bringing on the one hand, the commons knowledge and on the other hand, policy and practice closer in Europe & CIS and beyond. IASC Europe & CIS wanted in this way also to support the communication among IASC members to facilitate content-based exchange and cross-disciplinary networking. The colloquium was announced via e-mail to the members of the IASC Europe and CIS network and members were asked to submit policy relevant topics. We then received several submissions which we selected and finally seven themes were used to be presented in relation to policies: urban commons, European agrarian commons, implementation of commons policies, health commons, digital commons and the SDGs and the commons (see table below).

All colloquium meetings took place on Thursdays via Zoom and in total we had seven meetings ranging including in total 13 presenters: Each of the colloquium sessions lasted 90 minutes. IASC members who proposed a respective topic provided an input of 30 - 45 minutes on the topic and on ideas how to address the policy dialogue. After each input we had 45 minutes to one hour for discussions and further planning. Reading materials of a specific topic were proposed online before the meeting.

Background for the colloquium was the fact that at the moment many policies related to agrarian subsidies, sustainable development goals, biodiversity protection, energy strategies, land use planning etc. are being discussed in Europe and CIS on national or on EU and other respective supranational levels. Europe and CIS is also closely linked to development policies in other regions through its active role in bilateral and global processes. Some of these policies are already on the way to be implemented by governments. Many of these issues are closely related to the commons but this is often not mentioned. Despite Ostrom's work, the commons are not an issue in these policies although highly relevant, especially when it comes to the issue of common property and commoners' interests. The presentation addressed these issues and discussions were focused on how this could be changed.

The presenters and their titles as well as their affiliations are listed in the table below.

Overview of dates, names and topics

2022	Name	Title of the proposed presentation
17.03	Ana Rosa Chagas Cavalcanti (<i>University of São Paulo, Brazil</i>) Matteo Roggero (<i>Humboldt University, Germany</i>)	Commons and Polycentric Governance within and across cities
24.03	Antonio Manzoni (<i>St. Anna School of Advanced Studies, Italy</i>) Ignacio J. Diaz-Maroto (<i>University of Santiago de Compostela, Spain</i>) Nevenka Bogataj (<i>Slovenian Institute for Adult Education, Slovenia</i>)	The European commons: The “great absent” in the EU agri-food and agri-environmental policy making
31.03	Prathiwi Putri (<i>University of Kassel, Germany</i>)	Water as commons in undemocratic postcolonial South
07.04	Giuseppe Micciarelli (<i>University of Salerno, Italy</i>) Pablo Mendez (<i>University of Valencia, Spain</i>)	Success and failures in policy implementation – Methodological questions and sharing goals with commoners
21.04	Fabio Balli (<i>Concordia University, Canada</i>) Pascal Carpentier (<i>Erasmus University Rotterdam, Netherlands</i>)	Healing and law-making: re-creating collective narratives
28.04	Alex Pazaitis (<i>Tallinn University of Technology, Estonia</i>)	Is the digital economy market-driven or commons-based? Lessons for EU digital strategy
05.05	Tobias Haller (<i>University of Bern, Switzerland</i>) Ilkhom Soliev (<i>Martin Luther University of Halle-Wittenberg, Germany</i>)	SDGs and the commons: From a central missing topic towards recognition via national implementations?

We had between 16-35 persons in the meetings with presentations and lively discussions moderated by Ilkhom Soliev and Tobias Haller, which were also recorded. This document is a summary of texts that reflect each topic and also some of the discussions taking place during the online meetings. Each text was written by the respective presenters independently and represent their positions of the debate and discussions that took place during the colloquium series. The compilation is thus not a coherent publication but serves the purpose to inform about the several issues presented and discussed, based on individual contributions we have received.

Commons and Polycentric Governance within and across Cities

Ana Rosa Chagas Cavalcanti (University of São Paulo, Brazil)

1. The importance of the common good(s) in the 21st Century

The topic of the common goods acquires a particular importance in the 21st century. The economic crisis of 2008 has brought back the discussion on common goods (Harvey, 2011, p.85-86; De Moor, 2013, p.5; Stavrides, 2016; xiii-xiv), to many academic disciplines such as economics, law studies, philosophy and also architecture and urbanism - in a contemporary society marked by an 'economic transition' (Swilling & Annecke, 2012). The effects of such crisis affect many spheres of the social, economic and political life of human beings. According to some branches of philosophy, in the past 20th century, such unprecedented crisis would be dealt by citizens by focusing on two 'meta-narratives': the revolution (for those left wing oriented) versus the 'defence of the nation' (for those right wing oriented) (Ferry apud Sommet Sauver Le Bien Commun, 2021). However, the society of the 21st century is characterized by the end of meta-narratives and mass discourses (Ferry apud Common Good Summit, 2021). In such a pulverized and self-centred society, everyone seems to have a voice but it is more difficult to be heard. In this sense, the 'defence of the common good' appears to be the sole meta-narrative which is capable to unify those individualized citizens. This is because the preservation of our finite common resources, or even the defence of the common welfare of society, for example, are necessary to safeguard future generations in order to 'address the urgent ecological, social, economic and political facets of the crisis' (such as the scarcity of resources, unemployment, poverty, political crisis, among other challenges) (Ferry apud Common Good Summit, 2021). In fact, the commons are described by some authors as the 'revolution' of the 21st century (Dardot and Laval, 2017). Moreover, the commons opposes authoritarian or anarchic regimes, which are challenges in an extremely independent and non-unified contemporary society of the 21st century' (Piketty & Giraud, 2021, May 31st).

Hence, the defence of the commons seems to be a possible meta-narrative of the 21st century. For this reason, the common goods are not only currently the subject of interest of various disciplines (such as economics, political theory, philosophy, law studies and architecture and urbanism), but it is also being investigated in the realm of various schools of thought (Neoclassicism, Marxism, Keynesianism, Post Structuralism...) (Caffentzis & Frederici, 2014, p 92-93). In economic theory, the study about the common goods is often attributed to the school of thought of neoclassicism, notably to the studies of 2009's Nobel laureate in economic science, Elinor Ostrom. Ostrom has demonstrated how small institutions formed by citizens are able to successfully govern common goods and avoid the '*tragedy of the commons*' (Ostrom, 1990). By doing so, she challenged a previous scholarly belief: that the '*tragedy of the commons*' could only be avoided by regulating or privatizing the common goods, as pointed by Garret Hardin (Hardin, 1969). Hence, Ostrom's theory on the 'governance of the commons' is often applied to point out the failures of both state and market in the 21st century, because it focuses on a third way to manage common resources (Cavalcanti, 26th August 2021). As such, the commons address the failures of state and market and also show an alternative way of governing, in which small institutions formed by people are capable to manage common resources and to guarantee a common welfare in society.

2. The power of small institutions in the contemporary city

Cities are regulated and governed by logics of state and/or market. Analogously, the study of common goods demonstrate the power of collective institutions to govern the cities beyond those logics (which were mostly challenged amidst the stock market crisis of 2008). The rise of collective institutions composed by citizens who directly take care, co-create, co-plan or govern the city has been observed in the previous decade. Most of those communities are informal and are not supported by a solid policy or legal framework, especially in the case of the global south (particularly in Latin America) which is often cited as an interesting laboratory of urban commons by some authors (Frederici, 2014, 23rd October; Stavrides, 2016, 159-182; Peets & Azarhoosh, 2019, p.10). Those are, for example, social movements, collectives of people, or single individuals or groups of people who manage the common resources or act collectively for the care and

common welfare, as a strategy of survival (Stavrides, 2021). Collective occupations, squatter settlements, collective interventions in public space (such as urban farming, co-housing and other forms of micro-planning and tactical planning) and, appropriations of infrastructures and material matters of the city, are mostly claims of citizens for basic services and rights, such as the right to housing, the right to access basic infrastructures of the city, to nutrition, to leisure, to health and to education – in a direct and faster dialogue with respect to the mature timings of macro institutional politics and of technocratic state.

On the other hand, policies and regulatory frameworks which allow the management of common goods (and that guarantee a common welfare) have been implemented in Italy since many years due to a specific legal framework. That framework allows for the management and care of the common goods and is applied to individuals and communities who aim to care, co-planning, co-create, or use urban commons, besides of directly linking citizens' actions with public administration and their support (Arena, 2021). The applied definition of common good recognizes the material and immaterial resources of the city and its infrastructures (which are understood as common resources), but also the individuals and the collective organizations (commoners) which guarantees a welfare for the city and their communal actions. In fact, jurist Stefano Rodotà stresses that the commons is not so much related to issues of ownership and property (nor to matters of goods or resources), but it is rather understood as 'the management of common goods,' which 'has to allow for the development of human beings': that is, the key aspect here is to switching the notion of 'common goods' from 'goods' to 'regimes' (Rodotà, 2009) – as Ostrom did. Those laws and public policies are anchored by the principle of 'subsidiarity' (2001), which composes an amendment in the Italian Constitution that allow citizens to intervene in areas of the city (public spaces for common purposes), whenever the state fails to provide services or infrastructures.

Legal instruments such as the '*patti di collaborazione*' (pacts of collaboration), the '*regolamento sulla collaborazione tra cittadini e amministrazione per la cura e la rigenerazione dei beni comuni urbani*' (regulation for the care and regeneration of the commons), demonstrate that a governance of the city by citizens is possible. Those are driven by 'active citizens' who establish a relationship of trust with the state (Arena 2006). The collective institutions carry on several activities, starting from using dismissed areas of the cities and dwellings for a common purpose (and as a common good) to allowing citizens to access goods and services in an inclusive manner (Arena, 2021). Those actions are related to the concept of direct democracy and to participatory practices of citizens (Ciaffi, D. personal communication, 12th May 2022; Arstein, 1969). Such public policies intervene in the fissures of market and state, allowing citizens to perform their rights and promote a collective use of the city in a direct and fast manner, as a collective institution. In this sense, legal supports and the public policies related to the commons do not only address political divisions in society (because they allow to concentrate in urgent and necessary challenges which are needed to the survival of mankind), but they also may foster virtuous ways of practicing and living the city by nurturing the political life of citizens. That is: the direct participation of active citizens in the care, the co-creation and the management of the city are not only a third way of building cities, but they also nurture a public life.

For this reason, public space (and the public life of human beings) are fundamental to the success of public policies related to the defence of the commons. Without public life, values and practices such as innovation, participation, democracy and politics, cannot exist nor resist, since public space is the nest of the commons, of democracy and political life, and the idea of state and of the city (Arendt, 1969, pp 50-58). As such, public space is the spatial and temporal dimension of communal life and the city are the summary of the social, political and ecological struggles. The political space is the outcome of the collective spatial and temporal dimension of the life of citizens and it is in the city that they clash (Montaner & Muxi, 2021: p. 30).

3. The role of the city and public space to collective institutions, governance and political life: Cities as Common Goods by Definition

Public space has a crucial role in the political life of human beings, which is defined by the philosopher Hannah Arendt as a common life (Arendt, 1969, pp 50-58). This is often not mentioned by scholars but it is rather an important point on the role of urban space to the theory of the common good. According to the

philosopher Aristotle, virtues such as truth, respect and kindness among many other communal and community values, depend on public life, and are the outcome of the encounter of individuals with people with different points of view and experiences. As such, living a public life is important for the political, for the social and for the psychological development of human beings. This is what Arendt describes as a common life, as opposed to private life and private space: a people's contact with instincts, individuality, and intimate life (Arendt, 1969). Analogously, the decrease of public spaces and public life, and the lack of interest of citizens in participating in its care, in its political dimension, in its institutional processes and in actively using, caring and living the city, may be an outcome of the extreme speculation of the city by market logics in the 21st century, which transforms every single corner of the city into a possibility of speculation. An important remark thought, is that such may represent the death of both democracy, the idea of state, of the virtues and political life of a people, of the commons and of the city by definition (as the summary of the intellectual and practical capacities and potential of human life and practices, as a human collective outcome and a social product).

As such, any change in institutional and policy frameworks towards a common city directly pervades the defence of the city by definition itself (a collective institution), especially its public spaces and its public life. Because the city is the epitome of the commons, either understood as a common weal being but also as collective institutions framed by citizens, and it is a powerful matter for the defence of common resources and the common weal being.

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References

- Arena, G. (2006). *Cittadini Attivi*. Editori Laterza.
- Arena, G. (2020). *I Custodi della Bellezza: Prendersi Cura dei Beni Comuni*. Milano: Touring Club Milano.
- Arendt, H. (1958). *The Human Condition*. The University of Chicago Press.
- Aristotle (2020). *Ética a Nicômaco*. Principis.
- Arstein, S. (1969). The Ladder of Citizen Participation. *Journal Of The American Planning Association*. s/l, p. 216-224. jul. 1969.
- Cafentzis, G. ; Frederici, S. (2014). Commons against and beyond capitalism. *Community Development Journal*. Vol. 49. N. SI. January 2014, pp 92-105.
- Cavalcanti, A. R. C (2021, 26th August). Aprendendo com os bens comuns/ Learning with the Commons 'FAU em PROSA' on the 26th August 2021 [Video]. Youtube: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=S3Q_8sS0tZE
- Ciaffi, D. (2022, 12th May). Take care of Commons: The Italian way of participation. Lecture given to the course 'AUH0545 Aprendendo com os Bens Comuns/Learning with the Commons', on the 12th May 2022. São Paulo-Torino, 2022.
- Dardot P.; Laval, C. (2017). *Comum: ensaio sobre a Revolução no século 21*. Boitempo.
- De Moor, T. (2013). *Homo Cooperans. Institutions for collective action and the compassionate society*. Utrecht University.
- De Sponville, A. C. (2021). 'Ques-ce que le bien commun?'. *Sommet Sauver Le Bien Commun*. 27-28 May 2021. Toulouse School of Economics, Toulouse, France. Available online at: <https://www.commongoodsummit.com>
- Ferry, L. (2021). 'Ques-ce que le bien commun?'. *Sommet Sauver Le Bien Commun*. 27-28 May 2021. Toulouse School of Economics, Toulouse, France. Available online at: <https://www.commongoodsummit.com>

- Frederici, S. (2014, 23rd October). ‘*The Struggle for the Commons.*’ Interview broadcast at Kontext TV [Video]. Youtube: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oJwFT3a3J_4
- Hardin, G. (1968). The Tragedy of the Commons. *Science* 162 (3859), (June), 1243–1248. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.162.3859.1243>
- Harvey, D. (2013). *Rebel Cities: From the Right to the City to Urban Revolution.* Verso Books.
- Montaner J. M., Muxi, Z. (2021). *Politica e Arquitetura: Por um urbanismo do comum e ecofeminista.* Olhares.
- Ostrom, E. (2011). *Governing the Commons: the Evolution of Institutions for Collective Action.* Cambridge University Press.
- Piketty, T.; Giraud, G. (2021, May 31st). Le capitalisme est-il reformable? *Institut Rousseau, 31st May 2021.* [Video]. Youtube: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0nbvO3poSwc>
- Rodotà, S. (2009). Commissione Rodotà sui beni pubblici. Senato Italiano, Italy. Available online at: <https://polser.files.wordpress.com/2014/02/commissione-rodot.pdf>
- Stavrides, S. (2016). *Common Space: The City as Commons.* Zed Books.
- Smets P. ; Azzarhoosh, F. (2019). Urban commons and commoning in Amsterdam East: The role of liquid communities and the local government. *Sociologia E Politiche Sociali*, 22(1), 91-109.
- Swilling, M.; Annecke, E.(2012). *Just Transitions: Explorations of sustainability in an unfair world.* UTC Press.

The European Commons: The “great absent” in the EU Agri-food and Agri-environmental Policy Making

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1. Commons as an absent category in EU-Agri-Structures:

According to EUROSTAT (2013), approximately 9 million hectares of EU land is constituted by customary common lands (pastures, grazing lands, forests). This means about 7% of the total Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA). This percentage rises to even 9-10% of the EU territory, if we account also coasts and forests. An example of extent and forms of collective management of forests is given in the latest global report on forest ownership (FAO UNECE 2020). Besides, in the last decades several examples of more contemporary commons have been flourishing all over Europe (CSAs, urban gardens, and closely related initiatives, mostly embracing agroecology). Common land governance offers a greener, more sustainable, and resilient alternative to intensive agricultural land tenure systems, which is why most collective lands across Europe are considered officially protected (e.g., under the Natura 2000 Framework). However, there is not even a single mention of the commons neither in the incoming CAP (2023-2027) nor in the EU Green Deal with its associated strategies (Biodiversity & Farm to Fork Strategies, Climate Law, etc.). We claim that this “invisible reality” of the commons cannot be ignored, especially in light of its new environmental ambitious targets. Both contemporary and customary commons can constitute a point of departure for the EU to develop socially inclusive instruments that are sensitive to ecology. We illustrate sustainable and resilient rural development on this basis by two case studies from Slovenia and Spain.

2. The Slovenian Case

Slovenian example of commons refers to collective management of pastures and forests on less productive sites. Voluntary, self-organized and peer-mediated local production bases on both, productive and non-productive values and has specific form of democratic organization that characterizes rural tradition. However, their national jurisdiction framed into agricultural sector poorly recognizes local collective rules and there is no statistics for this type of management. Commoners are under-represented in decision-making which is not a surprise in any post-socialist country after decades of abolition. Common lands are characterized with general reluctance of landowners to enter organizations and slow revival of their type of governance. Roles of old and new commons for rural resilience are not acknowledged as potentials. Natura 2000 protects 37% of the Slovenian territory- while commons are absent in public discourse and a subject of tensions between rural income potentials from agriculture, tourism, and nature protection.

3. The Spanish case

The communal lands of northwest Iberian Peninsula – “baldios” in Portugal and “Montes Veciñais en Man Común” (MVMC) in Galicia – play a vital role in the economy of the communities. This function was lost during the twentieth century because the forestation of them and the decline of agriculture. The restoration of democratic regimes returned them to their original owner communities, now in decline, aged and disorganized. Communal lands occupy near 1 million ha, 400,000 in north Portugal and 600,000 in Galicia with high average areas (500 ha in Portugal and 200 ha in Galicia). They are owned by around 2900 communities in Galicia and 1000 in north Portugal. The use is mainly forestry, but numerous reasons caused in a sub-utilization of their potential. Both Galician and Portuguese case show similarities and complementary benefits needing socioeconomic innovation to make better use of rural resilience. The commons and small-scale business initiatives could support the network of the local produce markets with attractive values, as well as contribute to the conservation of the biodiversity.

References

General

- Bassi, I., Carestiato, N. (2016). Common property organisations as actors in rural development: a case study of a mountain area in Italy. *International Journal of the Commons* 10(1): 363-386. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.18352/ijc.608>
- Bassi, M. (2012). Recognition and Support of ICCAs in Italy. In: A. Kothari and others (eds). *Recognizing and Supporting Territories and Areas Conserved by Indigenous Peoples And Local Communities: Global Overview and National Case Studies*. Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity, ICCA Consortium, Kalpavriksh, and Natural Justice, Montreal, Canada. Technical Series no. 64, 160 pp.
- European CSA Research Group (2016). Overview of Community Supported Agriculture in Europe. Available at: <http://urgenci.net/the-csa-research-group/>
- EUROSTAT (2013). Common lands survey statistics. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Farm_structure_survey_%E2%80%933_common_land#Statistics_on_common_land
- Jackson, P., Rivera, M.G., Candel, J., et al. (2021). Food as a commodity, human right or common good. *Nature Food* 2: 132-134. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-021-00245-5>
- SAPEA (2020). A Sustainable Food System for the European Union. Available at: <https://www.sapea.info/topics/sustainable-food/>
- Vivero, J.L. (2017). The Food Commons in Europe: relevance, challenges, and ideas to feed them. P2P Foundation Ed. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/309859724_The_Food_Commons_in_Europe_Relevance_Challenges_and_Ideas_to_Feed_Them

Slovenia

- Bogataj, N. (2012). Model delovanja slovenskih agrarnih skupnosti. In: Rodela, R. (Ed): *Soupravljanje naravnih virov: vaške skupnosti in sorodne oblike skupne lastnine in skupnega upravljanja*. Wageningen, Wageningen University and Research Centre: 23-37
- Bogataj, N., Krč, J. (2014). A forest commons revival in Slovenia. *Society & Natural Resources* 27: 867-881.
- Gatto, P., Bogataj, N. (2016). Disturbances, robustness, and adaptation in forest commons: comparative insights from two cases in the South-eastern Alps. *Forest Policy and Economics* 58: 56-64.
- FAO UNECE (2020). *Who owns our forests? Forest ownership in the ECE region*. UNECE/FAO Forestry and Timber. United Nations Economic Commission for Europe. Geneva: Switzerland. Available at: <http://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/timber/publications/SP-43.pdf>
- Lawrence, A., Gatto, P., Bogataj, N., Lidestav, G. (2020). Forests in common: learning from diversity of community forest arrangements in Europe. *Ambio* 50: 448-464.
- Petek, F., Urbanc, M. (2007) Common land in Slovenia. *Geografski vestnik* 79(2), 41–62.
- Premrl, T., Udovč, A., Bogataj, N., Krč, J. (2015). From restitution to revival: A case of commons re-establishment and restitution in Slovenia. *Forest Policy and Economics* 59, 19–26.
- Šmid Hribar, M., Kozina, J., Bole, D., Urbanc, M. (2018). Public goods, common-pool resources, and the commons: The influence of historical legacy on modern perceptions in Slovenia as a transitional society. *Urbani izziv* 29(1), 96–109.

Spain

- Antunes, P., Santos, R., Videira, N. (2006). Participatory decision making for sustainable development—the use of mediated modelling techniques. *Land Use Policy* 23: 44-52.
- Arnalte, E.V. (2002). PAC y desarrollo rural: una relación de amor-odio. *Información Comercial Española. ICE: Revista de economía* 803 (*Globalización y Mundo Rural*): 45-60.
- European Union (EU) (2006). Putting rural development to work for jobs and growth. EU-Directorate General for Agriculture and Rural Development. Newsletter Special Edition.
- Green, A.O., Hunton-Clarke, L. (2003). A typology of stakeholder participation for company environmental decision-making. *Business Strategy and the Environment* 12(5): 292-299.
- Kangas, J., Kangas, A. (2005). Multiple criteria decision support in forest management—the approach, methods applied, and experiences gained. *Forest Ecology and Management* 207(1-2): 133-143.
- Kelly, R., Moles, R. (2002). The Development of Local Agenda 21 in the Mid-west Region of Ireland: A case study in interactive research and indicator development. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management* 45(6): 889-912.
- Marey-Perez, M.F., Diaz-Varela, E., Calvo-Gonzalez, A. (2014). Does higher owner participation increase conflicts over common land? An analysis of communal forests in Galicia (Spain). *IForest-Biogeosciences and Forestry* 8: 533-543.
- Perz, S., Barnes, G., Shenkin, A. (2014). Private and communal lands? The ramifications of tenure ambiguity and regional integration for tenure formalization and its consequences in northern Bolivia. *International Journal of the Commons* 8(1): 179-206.

Water as Commons in Undemocratic Postcolonial South

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1. Demand for water commons

Following the two decades of water service privatization, the 21st Century has been marked with a wave of civil society movements, demanding for re-municipalization of the water service (Albalade et al. 2021; Lobina and Hall 2000). Re-municipalization has been referred as the processes to return water services to full public ownership, management and democratic control, to ‘resolve the trade-offs between shareholder and customer interests’ that were the key fundamental problem of water service privatization (Bakker 2008a). There is no single universal model of the public improvement trajectory, from privatization to re-municipalization, as the trajectory is highly shaped by the geo-history of public utilities, the nature of privatization contract (full or partial privatization), the urban characters of respective city, as well as the nature of civil society movement. Looking closer to the European context alone, there are subtle nuances of opportunities and problems within the diverse cases of re-municipalization (see for example Bauby et al. 2018).

Despite water re-municipalization has been a powerful strategy of anti-privatization movements (as successfully proven in Europe, the US and many parts of the Global South), there remain governance issues that are beyond the core concern of re-municipalization policy, such as water resources and water ecosystems, the role of state in pair with of communities as well as the needs for accountability and wider participation (Bakker 2008a, 2008b). Definitely, re-municipalization has a political meaning beyond its procedural success – that is to administratively return to the organizational form of public ownership. It opens up more opportunities for communities, or more public debates on how to involve communities, including experimentations on public-community partnerships.¹ Particularly, commons and the process of commoning have taken much space in this political debates (Bakker 2008b).

Scrutinizing the context of Jakarta, an example of cities in the Postcolonial South, there have been multiple major trajectories of water and sanitation service provisions at play. Water privatization in the 1990s involved two utilities of piped-water networks covering 65% of total area, but even within this coverage area the water supply is deemed low or not optimum. A wide array of diverse informal services fills in the gap: water vendors, informal workers of well diggers, informal permit arrangements for groundwater extractions, trading networks of water-bottles with community stalls, and so on. Informal practices operate by involving communities, but perhaps such irregular and under-regulated involvements are far from having the characters of commoning practices.

2. The Indonesian urban context and informal sectors

(Colonial) cities in Indonesia have emerged and expanded with a long history of community self-provision services (Putri 2019). Communities and their self-help infrastructures make the city, spatially marked within the agglomeration of the so-called informal settlements, or *kampung*; a *kampung* is an Indonesian term refers to village unit, or in the urban context, it was referring to settlements outside the colonial city that were inhabited by indigenous ethnic groups, the Arabs, Gujarati, other than the European and Chinese. Most *kampung*s are not served by the piped-water networks, although around 2007 there are attempts to connect to the houses for example through the GPOBA program of the World Bank.² With this program, a higher number of water subscriber was helped achieved but not the performance of the private utilities and the increase amount of water supply. Moreover, this was in practice merely turn the informal water market into a formal one without improvements of life-quality (my research notes 2012, 2017, 2018, interviews with communities and activists).

¹ tmi.org/en/publication/democratic-and-collective-ownership-of-public-goods-and-services

² gprba.org/news/us257-million-world-bank-administered-oba-grant-improved-access-water-services-western-jakarta

In kampungs there are practices of shared wells, among other water cultures of living along the river banks. River banks have long been the backside of the city, hence the affordable living place for those migrating from the hinterlands. A recent program named Normalisasi Sungai (river normalization) aimed at straightening the river fronts with concrete embankment. The infrastructure project was developed at the expense of community evictions. More than 300 cases of forced evictions aided by armed personnel happened in 2015 and 2016, rupturing more than 80,000 homes and small-scale business units in the Indonesian capital city. The evictions cleared the space up including for the city beautification programmes and for the upper-class consumption infrastructures, for example in the forms of water-front asphalt roads and public squares with commercial functions.

Along with the demolishment of houses and working spaces, their water culture was erased from the urban landscape. A significant number of the evicted households have been forcibly moved into high-rise social housing blocks and subscribed to the piped-water network, leaving them in debt for the housing rents and water bills.

In the meantime, Jakarta a city on a delta is under environmental pressures: regular flooding and drought (despite an abundance of precipitation), land subsidence in the time of sea-level rise, heavy pollutants in surface water and groundwater. Modern technologies within the hard-infrastructure approach to water supply, while in a highly neglect of proper sanitation infrastructure (only less than 1% of development budget in the sanitation sector nationwide), leave the needs for water conservation and water resource management behind. The extractive behavior, or separating clean water as product and treating the rest components of the water cycle as waste, being out of care, is not merely the story in the city. The archipelago has turned into a landscape of dams.

3. State interventions: postcolonial landscape of dams

Dams, water reservoirs and canals in the archipelago have been the modernist symbol of (colonial) progress and prosperity. In Java alone, there are 86 dams built and utilized for irrigation, domestic and industrial clean water supply and electricity generation. Not only large dams have taken over community productive lands, they have also destroyed community water systems. As in the story of urban kampungs, first they grab the land, second the water. It is however rarely addressed within the policy, the unity of land-water grabbing. The number above excludes the newly planned dams in 24 locations, to increase water security in Java the most populated island, as reported by Hasan and Ridwan (2021). This report suggests a significant improvement for irrigation by channeling water from these dams. However, this is one side of the story. Below is a rather bigger picture of the whole cycle of dam development. Below is a bigger picture of the destructive cycle of dam development, as exemplified with the case of Wadas mining for the development of Bener Dam, which is a supporting infrastructure to supply the needs for water of the new airport in Yogyakarta Province. Excerpts of presentation slides, below, show diagrams and figures from *Project Multatuli*, a progressive journalistic platform that promotes the spirits of commoning knowledge.

Source:
<https://projectmultatuli.org/tanah-surga-wadas-dijadikan-tambang-mengapa-pemerintah-menindas-petani/>
 Accessed 16.02.2022 16:50 CET

Communities of Wadas Village have been opposing against the stone mining. The extraction is meant to provide materials to build the new dam Bendungan Bener that will take over 313 hectares of land. The Dam will be the main water and energy source for the newly built airport in Yogyakarta the city of universities and tourism. Productive landscapes with community forests and farming are at danger. Water security has been modelled at the expense of food security, while the purpose of water provision is to enhance economic growth. Below is a glance of Wadas biodiversity and community productions.

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4. Community as the unit for commoning

There is urgent needs to address water as a holistic circle of socio-nature assemblages, instead of addressing it as separated, detached sub-sectors or products of clean water supply, drainage, sanitation, power generation and irrigation. Water as commons might be an alternative concept to the dichotomy of water as public or private goods, as well as to imagine the world of water beyond the modernist infrastructure regimes with their separated products or commodities. If commoning water to be seen as a form of social-ecological movement, forging a new policy paradigm that promotes citizen control over water, one crucial step is to recognize community at the center for realizing water as commons. Experiences have shown that one factor for the success of common-pool resource water management is a relatively small community settled in or attached to a well-defined boundaries of water resource. Cooperative institutions might be the embedded model of management in this community-led water management. Perhaps this is not merely a form of decentralized technologies as the alternative to the centralized piped-networks. The community unit will operate not only for extracting water or distilling clean water from its socio-ecosystems, but also to guard the interlinked components within the holistic cycle of water. In here perhaps we can see a new role of the state, not as the main regulatory body (as communities will also be part of the regulatory institution), to build the capacity of communities. Diverse forms of informalities need to undergo transformations towards potentials for commoning water resources. This is not merely a theoretical concern but also empirical questions. Hence, there have to be experimentations on the ground to be evaluated and contested, and further improved.

References

- Albalade, Daniel; Bel, Germà; Gradus, Raymond; Reeves, Eoin (2021): Re-municipalization of local public services: incidence, causes and prospects. In *International Review of Administrative Sciences* 87 (3), pp. 419–424. DOI: 10.1177/00208523211006455.
- Bakker, Karen (2008a): The Ambiguity of Community: Debating Alternatives to Private-Sector Provision of Urban Water Supply. In *Water Alternatives* 1 (2).
- Bakker, Karen (2008b): The“Commons” Versus the“Commodity”: Alter-Globalization, Anti-Privatization and the Human Right to Water in the Global South. In Becky Mansfield (Ed.): *Privatization*. Oxford, UK: Blackwell Publishing Ltd, pp. 38–63.
- Bauby, Pierre; Hecht, Christina; Warm, Stephanie (2018): Water remunicipalisation in Berlin and Paris. Specific processes and common challenges.
- Hasan, Mohamad; Ridwan, Dadang (2021): Water security on Java island. In *Irrigation and Drainage* 70 (3), pp. 370–379.
- Lobina, Emanuele; Hall, David (2000): Public Sector Alternatives to Water Supply and Sewerage Privatization: Case Studies. In *International Journal of Water Resources Development* 16 (1), pp. 35–55. DOI: 10.1080/07900620048554.
- Putri, Prathiwi (2019): Sanitizing Jakarta: decolonizing planning and kampung imaginary. In *Planning Perspectives* 34 (5), pp. 805–825.

Success and Failures in Policy Implementation – Methodological questions and Sharing Goals with Commoners

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1. The commons and policy influences

On the one hand there is a commons explosion, on the other a growing confusion and perhaps risk of distortion of their meaning when they are included (or excluded) in policy or grassroots claims. We are in a *Participatory Zeitgeist* (Palmer et al 2019) or *co-biquity* (Williams et.al.) 2020), which is often confused and overlapped with the discourse of the commons.

On the other hand, there is an underestimation of the commons. It is neither the first nor the last time that public policies underestimate the importance of the theoretical and practical lexicon of the commons. Keywords such as “commons” in a regulatory text does not mean anything by itself, and in some cases can even be misleading or represent a case of “commons washing” (Micciarelli 2021).

So, a first question arises: what does it mean to influence policy? A first hypothesis is that influencing policy is about influencing laws and norms that affect the commons. Then we should focus on those rules and norms that specifically influence the management and use of that particular type of interdependent, rival and non-excludable material and immaterial resources that are managed through collective institutions. I believe this should be a starting point, but not an end goal. Indeed, studying the commons certainly means investigating the success and failure of experiences of collective governance of an interdependent commons resource. But when we talk about policy, looking 'inside' the commons, i.e. at their institutional patterns, is no longer sufficient. Talking about policy means analysing the legal, economic and social environment around them.

The regulations that influence the commons are never just about these: tax regulations, phyto-sanitary regulations, urban planning regulations and regulations for the use of abandoned real estate, laws on the management of water services, environmental protection and many other laws influence different types of commons, but never just these. These are always categories and regulations that affect broader reference contexts, e.g. the environment, healthcare, communities, the economic and production system, workers' rights and consumers' rights. It is in these broader fields that there are rules that challenge the existence of institutional structures of commons management. This applies to both the new commons (such as the urban commons or the knowledge commons) and the 'traditional' commons.

2. Developing rules

If we consider this correct, we can then advance a second hypothesis. To influence policy means not only to protect the specificity of certain types of resources, but to develop rules that from commons can influence other, more general policies. In other words, we should promote a commons perspective that empowers rules not only for the commons, but for their legal-economic environment of reference, protect certain key good as functional for the exercise of fundamental rights of present and future generations (Rodotà 2012).

Here may arise the ability of commons not only to be “accepted” by the mainstream regulatory frameworks, but even to transform those regulatory systems that often ignore them or marginalize them. In order to create spaces of autonomy for the commons we must act directly towards the State and the Market, proposing reforms and policies that can transform both.

This second hypothesis is therefore both ambitious and necessary. In order to give it a chance, however, we must first advocate the first hypothesis: influencing policies that directly affect what we consider to be the commons. This can mean many things. A sign of policy success is its ability to enable and strengthen experiences (potential or ongoing) of commons use and management, and that those are done in a sustainable way.

What does it mean to investigate and remove the legal and political obstacles that commoners face in the different complex governance frameworks? My thesis is that, as scholars, we succeed in influencing public policy when our target is the empowerment of the subjects engaged in the case studies we analyze. Our task is not only to describe what works in those processes of self-organization, but as Elinor and Vincent Ostrom's research shows, also to understand which elements are crucial for their success.

3. Studying obstacles

In my perspective, in order to implement the commons, it is therefore necessary to elaborate, together with the commoners, strategies for changing the broader economic and legal system.

This means studying the legal and economic obstacles that hinder the processes of self-organization and analyzing scenarios for bringing changes that not only legitimize the experiences of collective management of the commons, biodiversity protection, and participative land use planning, but also encourage and incentivize them.

The commons are behind the State and the market, but they are not impermeable to them. Their governance is deeply influenced by that of the state and the market. For this reason, I have studied sectors of governance very different from those related to the commons, in particular free trade agreements and connected neoliberal institutional changes.

In this sense, we have to question policies by intervening in the funding and legislation of local, national and international public bodies. It is fundamental for many commons-sectors, I mention for all that of the water service, which we spoke about in one of our Colloquim.

On this we can imagine funding as IASC a project to study and collect international precedents: best practices and legislation that protect the commons, starting with their legal status.

I will now make some brief considerations in the field where I have experimented with this approach. I refer to urban commons. The reuse of under-utilised or abandoned real estate and areas directly concerns the vision of the city, the relationship between property rent and public authorities, the economy of large cities, urban regeneration, tourism, urban security and areas of very high poverty.

It is clear that in the urban commons we are affecting all these issues. The issue of governance concerns both the governance of the commons and the governance of cities. Governance is always relating to an intertwining of the global and the local. To understand one of the two, it must be situated in light of the transformations of the other. From this perspective, we need to focus on governance institutional changes starting from the evolution of contemporary local governance. The connections between politics and law in the urban commons will be key to understanding this broader scenario.

4. Legal hacking as methodology

On this field, I worked on a methodology that is related to the “legal hacking” (the so called “creative use of law”). In this field, a good example is the new legal instrument of collective governance: the so called “urban and collective civic use” started in the city of Naples, by precisely enhancing a tool of governance of collective and rural properties.

The methodology of legal hacking is not a lobbying strategy. In fact, it is not only aimed at improving the dialogue with policy makers, but it is oriented towards building forms of collaboration between different commoning experiences in order to impose a regulatory change with the support of public opinion. So legal hacking is oriented towards imposing regulatory changes creatively using law—in this way both influencing concrete commons governance. This connects policies on the commons to regulations on participatory and deliberative democracy (in their diversity). It is no coincidence that many regulations concerning the urban commons are connected to civic participation policies.

One of the great obstacles in policy-making is the huge variation that can exist between commons that are very different from each other. It therefore appears essential to distinguish more clearly between two macro-types of commons, to which two different approaches to policy are related.

Emerging commons are goods that are functional to the direct exercise of social, economic, and political rights, used in non-exclusive forms and through a collective governance that distributes rights between an open community of commoners in a non-rivalistic and cooperative way. The legislative context must enable their special governance regime, encouraging and guaranteeing the establishment of collective civic management and popular assembly bodies, which constitute a new horizon of democratic self-government. Examples are ex-urban or rural places refunctionalized as spaces for the claiming and exercise of rights and of collective fulfilment.

Necessary commons are goods that are functional to the exercise of fundamental rights. Their public ownership must be preserved. Where they are private, they should be subject to collective use, through easement or else exceptions should be made or licences and/ or patents granted to allow for them to be established for non-commercial purposes. In order to guarantee and reinforce their 'common' dimension, international treaties and laws must recognize participatory governance, which includes those for whom those goods are indispensable via their representatives, associations, groups, or public and private institutions. They might be tangible, intangible, or knowledge commons. Examples include water resources, vaccines, and all life-saving drugs (Macciarelli 2022)

So *Urban commons* are emerging commons located in "ex places", urban e rural areas and real estate collectively used by community based organization where non-excludability is the output of a political choice linked to an anti-rival cooperative governance, since they are very often huge and there are shared because the cooperation is needed to manage them. I believe that the limits in our ability to influence public policy also concern the inability to influence public discourse in a broader sense.

In this regard, the category of emerging commons is an open category, which can have media impact. This can also produce self-recognition there practitioners, citizens and cooperatives as part of commons perspective. This is also the first step towards greater institutional recognition of the commons.

References

- Micciarelli, G. (2021) *Democrazia partecipativa e «Commons Washing»*. *Un confronto critico sul rapporto tra organizzazioni comunitarie e istituzioni*, in "Iride, Filosofia e discussione pubblica" 1/2021, pp. 93-105, doi: 10.1414/101254
- Micciarelli, G. (2022) *Hacking the legal. The commons between the governance paradigm and inspirations drawn from the 'living history' of collective land use*, in A. Ferreira, F. Savini, & K. von Schonfeld K. (Eds.), *Post-growth planning: towards an urbanisation beyond the market economy*. Routledge, forthcoming 2022).
- Palmer VJ, Weavell W, Callander R, Piper D, Richard L, Maher L, Boyd H, Herrman H, Furler J, Gunn J, Iedema R, Robert G. The Participatory Zeitgeist: an explanatory theoretical model of change in an era of coproduction and codesign in healthcare improvement. *Med Humanit.* 2019 Sep;45(3):247-257.
- Rodotà, S. (2012) *Il diritto di avere diritti*, Laterza
- Williams, O., Sarre, S., Papoulias, S.C. *et al.* (2020) Lost in the shadows: reflections on the dark side of co-production. *Health Res Policy Sys* 18, 43 (2020).

Health and Law-making: Collectively Re-creating Narratives

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1. Introduction

Since childhood, we learn that knowledge does not come from ourselves (schoolchildren), but from “an omniscient master”. When a crisis happens – a disease, a change in our environment – we similarly rely on external authorities, who are usually prompt to provide us with directives. But is this the most effective way to take care of our very needs to overcome complex challenges (Oxfam, 2021; V-Dem Institute, 2021; Rushkoff, 2019; Medina, 2013)? Can a few enlightened individuals be more knowledgeable than the multitude (Raymond, 1999; Okolloh 2009; Falkvinge 2013)?

Is the centralization of power during an emergency still legitimate when the Internet allows thousands of people to put in common their resources (e.g., online hackathons (Balli, 2021)), and to decide within hours (e.g., digital democracy (Manicini, 2015; European Parliament, 2020; TA Swiss et al., 2021))?

During this participatory discussion, we will explore the narratives behind “health” and “law” policy-making centralization. We will explore how people can reclaim ownership of themselves, control over their medical journey and medical information (e.g., health commons (Balli 2021a; b)), critical public health (Greenhalgh, 2009)). We will also discuss how individuals and communities can reclaim the right to elaborate rules that affect them and their coordination (legal commons, democratic constitutionalism (Bailey and Mattei, 2013; Vergara, 2020; Boal, 1999; Laugeri, 2020)).

Finally, we will reflect on Elinor Ostrom's (2009) statement that “a core goal of public policy should be to facilitate the development of institutions that bring out the best in humans”. Thus we will introduce the work done in other fields by legal scholars working on indigenous law (Canada, Switzerland) (Banville et al, 2020; Knoepfel and Sheweizer, 2015), and on changing propriety (Italy) with reflections on how this can inspire health commons policy development (Italian Ministry of Justice, 2007; Vercellone, 2020; Italian Court of Cassation, 2011).

We adopted a bottom-up approach to collectively building a Knowledge Commons (KC) for the colloquium. We organized the session for participants to discuss among themselves and report on their conclusions. We built sub-groups of 5-7 people to foster interaction among all participants (Aubé et al, 2011). Then, each sub-group presented its key discussion outcomes. This allowed us to aggregate different perspectives that you will find compiled hereunder in this paper. Our reflections are documented and available online, on a public [MediaWiki](#); it can be enriched autonomously by interested individuals (after [creating an account](#)). The content of this wiki is under a [Creative Commons Attribution ShareAlike 4.0 license](#). Additionally, MediaWiki is free/libre and open-source software (FLOSS) (Free Software Foundation, 2021; Open Source Initiative, 2017), which means interested communities can freely use, reproduce, enhance and adapt the software – another commons. Our intent is to remove barriers to access, production, and dissemination of knowledge around this topic. Our approach is aligned with the UNESCO (2021) recommendation on open science, which encourages discussions and co-creation of open scientific knowledge.

2. Recreating the narrative on Health regulation – First perspective: The medical regulation challenge

A private legal entity must comply with medical device regulations (US Food and Drug Administration [FDA], European Medicines Agency [EMA]) and manufacture and commercialize the medical device. Thus, medical device regulatory bodies require quality management systems often incompatible with a volunteer-based organization (Abuhav, 2018). Regulators acknowledge benefits from open-source hardware (OSH) communities; hence they progressively adapted their regulation first to frame the use of smartphones as medical devices (FDA, 2013), then they regulated the increasing use of 3D printing in the medical sector (FDA, 2018). Finally, during the COVID-19 pandemic, they proposed an emergency regime (e.g., building ventilators).

Still regulators' needs are extremely stringent and quite challenging to achieve for a community of volunteers. Conscious of these limitations, some regulators, like the Australian one, made a specific statement regarding Diabetes control systems (2018):

“We recognise that **health professionals cannot recommend DIY [do it yourself] technologies** to people with diabetes. Health professional recommendations should be for devices that have been approved through the regulatory process for safety and effectiveness. However, **there will always be some people who accept a level of risk and choose to take the DIY approach. These people should continue to receive support and care** from their diabetes healthcare professional and the health system.”

Opinion of the attendees and way forward: Our attendees collectively agreed that the Australian approach is an acceptable middle ground where transparency and responsibility allow each individual to make an informed decision regarding their own risk profile and decide whether or not to use a DIY device on itself.

Participants wondered to which extent the creation of standards could help to structure the OSH ecosystem to make the regulation lighter or easier to enforce.

Financing open-source projects: One of the challenges OSH communities face is the financial valuation of the goods they produce. Unlike FLOSS projects, OSH projects are cash intensive, and funds are rapidly needed to scale up a collective innovation. Unfortunately, Venture Capitals or Banks struggle with the estimation of community assets and are very reluctant in the absence of patents protecting these assets to invest in these open projects. Interestingly, when universities push innovations, they tend to be quickly enclosed by private entities if considered relevant.

Opinion of the attendees and way forward: Participants highlighted the role that health insurance could take in financing these cost-effective, innovative projects and globally encouraging open approaches.

Globally, securing fair compensation for volunteers investing time and energy in these open-source solutions has been confirmed as a concern by the group. The protection from free riding, particularly in the OSH field where copyright protection is only partial and patenting too costly, stood out as a legitimate concern. Very often, the absence of a market protects communities from the problem and limits their ability to make a significant impact.

Indeed, the most prominent issue for the future success of OSH communities in the health sector is related to regulatory bodies and the financial system. Regulators and financial system players must acknowledge the post-COVID-19 paradigm shift; an ever-increasing number of innovations can be created above and beyond the OSS world. Thus policymakers need to create the conditions to secure these innovations to allow them to thrive legally.

3. Recreating the narrative on Health regulation – Second perspective

Can we heal without redefining the rules that affect us? The purpose of medical regulations “to identify and monitor significant adverse events involving medical devices. The goals of the regulation are to detect and correct problems in a timely manner.” (FDA, 2020). Hence, another approach to tackle this aim is to align with the spirit of the law, rather than solely complying with the written code. Critical public health and democratic constitutionalism can provide valuable inputs to such questioning.

Critical public health is an approach that invites us to recognize and challenge socio-economic barriers to good health, exploring to which extent certain institutions, regulations, processes or agents may be oppressive or allies (Greenhalgh, 2009).

Here, we can reflect on **whether medical regulations increase or hinder the capacity of a community of peers to rapidly identify and mitigate risks** related to self- and mutual care, respectively the co-creation of shared knowledge and technologies. In fact, many quality management systems are often implemented by decision of a third-party, rather than by a collective agreement among all actors of the ecosystem. Hence, **most actors may not find an intrinsic motivation in implementing such an approach** (Gelinias, 1984).

Similarly, medical devices thought by experts without a continuing involvement of end users – including in strategic decision-making – may result in products that either do not fit local realities, or a long-term use (van Dulmen et al, 2007; Compton et al, 2018).

A community co-creating a technology for their peers rather than for profit will possibly cumulate different advantages: personal engagement and passion, the will to put in commons complementarities to build collective wisdom, and a personal concern in mitigating risks so that others may adopt the technology knowing the collective effort made, but also assuming a form of sovereignty in taking their part of responsibility over use of technology. Additionally, OSH peer production can help impoverished communities to access medtech, and adapt these to local contexts, thanks to the rights to use, repair, reproduce, improve, and adapt (He and al, 2021; Al-Faruque, 2022) – consequently reducing the cost of innovation (Moritz et al, 2019). Indeed, it “is a very important need to increase access to medical devices to meet healthcare needs” (World Health Organization, 2016).

Democratic constitutionalism is another approach that invites us to remember “the will of the people as having a higher constitutional value than the will of Parliament” (Bailey and Mattei, 2013). In fact, regulations are of much lesser priority in the hierarchy of law than the constitutional process.

CC BY-SA by F Balli. Inspired by [Capra E, Mattei U. The Ecology of Law](#). Adapted from [Banville MS, Lapalme J. Property Rights / Property Wrongs](#). Icons: Freepik at flaticon.

Here, we can reflect on the extent to which medical regulations are aligned with higher collective interests and legal principles. For example, the intensive resources required to obtain medical certifications hinders transdisciplinary communities motivated by the collective wellbeing to enter such processes, while industries may receive a certification even when putting people’s lives at risk (Lundh et al, 2012; Dhruva et al, 2009). OSH projects have an essential benefit in comparison to industry’s practices: a commitment to ensure gratis online access to the fabrication recipe of the device, and sometimes even to the full iteration process.

As one human out of two cannot afford essential medical care (World Bank and World Health Organization, 2017), looking critically at the socio-economic barriers to health, and reflecting on the sovereignty communities should have in co-creating knowledge and technologies for the commons is vital. Indeed, as Capra and Mattei (2015) suggest, “If the people were to understand the nature of law [and health] as an evolving common, reflecting local conditions and fundamental needs, they would care about it. People would understand that the law [and health are] too important to remain in the hands of organized corporate interests”.

In this regard, it may be interesting to draw parallels with the paradigm shift requested by the Italian Court of Cassation following the work done by the Rodotà Commission (Italian Ministry of Justice, 2007):

Where an immovable property, regardless of the owner, is, due to its intrinsic connotations [...] intended for the realization of the welfare state [...], this property is to be considered, beyond the now outdated perspective of Roman dominium and code-related ownership, “commons”, that is, regardless of the title of ownership, instrumentally linked to the realization of the interests of all citizens (Italian Court of Cassation, 2011, translated by Vercellone, 2020, p. 8).

Could we then envision an ecosystem where regulations would emerge from communities federated around the co-creation of freely reproducible knowledge and technologies?

Middle ages

medieval local customs → specific right to use / enjoy the fruits of a common good
 scientific curiosity → social constructivism, contextual

Industrial revolution

Napoleon civil code → excluding ownership of a good and its fruits
 scientific rationalism → post-positivism, universalism

Today?

Self-ignorance
 Myth of scarcity
 Competition
 IP
 (Inner) War

Collective wisdom
 Abundance
 Commoning
 Libre licences
 (Inner) Peace

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As the industrial revolution brought excluding ownership, universalism and technology solutions, it may be of interest to explore "Ancient Intelligence," notably , shared rights of use, non-written laws such as indigenous local customs, and solidarity-driven solutions (Banville et al, 2020; Knoepfel and Schweizer, 2015)?

4. Discussion and way forward

A consensus emerged amongst colloquium participants; a balance between top-down regulation and bottom-up agility and autonomy has to be found to individualize healthcare treatments and devices.

The central point in this debate was transparency on health-related matters. Without transparency on personal data produced and controlled within proprietary medical technologies, providing meaningful informed consent to personal data collection and management is highly challenging. Ultimately, the absence of openness prevents individuals from adequately assessing medical-related risks and making appropriate decisions.

The same way that Stallman transformed copyright laws into copyleft with an intellectual jujitsu and guaranteed individuals the liberty to use, study, modify and distribute a product of the mind (Betz and Edwards, 1996). This has to be translated in the hardware field to combine top-down and bottom-up paradigms.

References

Workshop material is accessible online at: [IASC Health and Law, Whiteboard](#) and on the WikiMedia page : https://houseofcommons.ch/wiki/index.php?title=Health_and_law-making:_collectively_re-creating_narratives

- Abuhav I. (2018). *ISO 13485: 2016: A Complete Guide to Quality Management in the Medical Device Industry*. CRC Press.
<https://www.routledge.com/ISO-134852016-A-Complete-Guide-to-Quality-Management-in-the-Medical-Device/Abuhav/p/book/9781138039179>
- Al-Faruque F. (2022). Medtech remanufacturing is the new battleground for right-to-repair advocates. *Regulatory News*.
<https://www.raps.org/news-and-articles/news-articles/2022/4/medtech-remanufacturing-is-the-new-battleground-fo>
- Bailey S, Mattei U. (2013). Social Movements as Constituent Power: The Italian Struggle for the Commons. *Indiana Journal of Global Legal Studies* 20(2).
<https://www.repository.law.indiana.edu/ijgls/vol20/iss2/14>
- Balli F, Ibbotson R, Chhabra V, Pimentel JP, Suturin V, Falcon L, Timm-Bottos J, Kellner E, Menon J, Matringe M, le Couedic C. (2021a). Open-source respiratory health commons. 15 projects communities can adapt, repair, reproduce for low cost medical care (libre and open-source tech). General meeting of the Global Alliance against chronic Respiratory Diseases 2020-2021. *Zenodo*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5515632>
- Balli F, Matringe M, le Couedic C, Schull J, Gautam S, Jandard P, Kellner E, Anastasaki A, Serada K, Brahmachari SK, Winter L, Lonchamp P, Schoeller F, Krishnakumar A, Greshake B, Lhoste K, Parot C, Jeanmaire G. (2021b). Health technology as commons: trustable, affordable, adaptable. Geneva Health Forum Open Village. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4327587>
- Balli F. (2021c). Global crises, democratic solutions—within days. Using Internet to empower citizens, reach popular consensus, and ensure democratic decision-making [Preprint]. *Zenodo*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5497574>
- Balli F. (2021d). Team-building and information flow for large groups such as online hackathons - Updated Feb 2021. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3743244>
- Banville MS, Lapalme J. (2020). Property Rights / Property Wrongs: Micro-Treaties with the Earth. Rethinking our responsibilities towards nature through land stewardship. *Dark Matters Laboratories*.
<https://provocations.darkmatterlabs.org/property-rights-property-wrongs-micro-treaties-with-the-earth-9b1ca44b4df>
- Betz D, Edwards J. (1996). “Richard Stallman discusses his public-domain [sic] Unix-compatible software system with BYTE editors,” *BYTE* (July,). (Reprinted on the GNU Project web site: <http://www.gnu.org/gnu/byte-interview.html>.)
- Boal A. (1999). *Legislative Theatre. Using performance to make politics*. Routledge.
<https://www.routledge.com/Legislative-Theatre-Using-Performance-to-Make-Politics/Boal/p/book/9780415182416>
- Capra F, Mattei U. (2015). *The Ecology of Law: Toward a legal system in tune with Nature and Community*. Berrett-Koehler. <https://www.bkconnection.com/books/title/the-ecology-of-law>
- Compton B, Barash DM, Farrington J, Hall C, Herzog D, Meka V, Rafferty E, Taylor K, Varghese A. (2018). Access to medical devices in low-income countries: Addressing sustainability challenges in medical device donations. *National Academy of Medicine Perspectives*.

<https://doi.org/10.31478/201807a>

- Dhruva SS, Bero LA, Redberg RF. (2009). Strength of study evidence examined by the FDA in premarket approval of cardiovascular devices. *JAMA* 302. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2009.1899>
- Diabetes Australia. (2018). Diabetes Australia position statement - DIY technology for type 1 diabetes. <https://static.diabetesaustralia.com.au/s/fileassets/diabetes-australia/ee67e929-5ffc-411f-b286-1ca69e181d1a.pdf>
- European Parliament. (2020). *Digital democracy Is the future of civic engagement online?* [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2020/646161/EPRS_BRI\(2020\)646161_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2020/646161/EPRS_BRI(2020)646161_EN.pdf)
- Falkvinge R. (2013). *Swarmwise. The tactical manual to changing the world*. CreateSpace. <https://falkvinge.net/files/2013/04/Swarmwise-2013-by-Rick-Falkvinge-v1.1-2013Sep01.pdf>
- Gelinat A. (1984). Evaluation et multirationalité. Dans C Paquet. Des pratiques évaluatives. NHP. https://cap.banq.qc.ca/notice?id=p%3A%3Ausmarcdef_0000017356&locale=fr
- Greenhalgh T. (2009). Patient and public involvement in chronic illness: beyond the expert patient. *BMJ* 338. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.b49>
- He S, Lai D, Lee J. (2021). The medical right to repair: the right to save lives. *The Lancet* 397(10281). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(21\)00445-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(21)00445-1)
- Italian Court of Cassation. (2011). *Blue Valley Srl vs Ministero delle Infrastrutture e dei Trasporti, Ministero dell'Economia e delle Finanze*. https://www.labsus.org/wp-content/uploads//images/M_images/sentenza3811.doc
- Italian Ministry of Justice. (2007). *Commissione Rodotà - per la modifica delle norme del codice civile in materia di beni pubblici*. https://www.giustizia.it/giustizia/it/mg_1_12_1.wp?contentId=SPS47617
- Knoepfel P, Schweizer R. (2015). Le local et le global : quatre défis de la codification du droit foncier dans le cadre du processus de rédaction du code civil suisse de 1907. In Ponsonnet M, Travési C. *Les conceptions de la propriété foncière à l'épreuve des revendications autochtones : possession, propriété et leurs avatars*. Pacific-Credo. <https://doi.org/10.4000/books.pacific.330>
- Laugeri M. (2020). Emerging Change: a new Transactional Analysis frame for effective dialogue at work. *Transactional Analysis Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03621537.2020.1726660>
- Lundh A, Sismondo S, Lexchin J, et al. (2012). Industry sponsorship and research outcome. *Cochrane Database Systematic Review* 12. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.MR000033.pub3>
- Mancini P. (2015). Why it is time to redesign our political system. *European View* 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12290-015-0343-9>
- Medina J. (2013). *The Epistemology of Resistance – Gender and Racial Oppression, Epistemic Injustice, and the Social Imagination*. Oxford. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199929023.001.0001>
- Moritz M. et al. (2019). On the Economic Value of Open Source Hardware – Case Study of an Open Source Magnetic Resonance Imaging Scanner. *Journal of Open Hardware* 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.5334/joh.14>
- Okolloh O. (2009). *Ushahidi or 'testimony': Web 2.0 tools for crowdsourcing crisis information. Participatory Learning and Action*. <https://pubs.iied.org/g02842>

- Ostrom E. (2009). Beyond markets and states: polycentric governance of complex economic systems. Prize lecture. *The Sveriges Riksbank Prize in Economic Sciences in Memory of Alfred Nobel*. https://www.nobelprize.org/uploads/2018/06/ostrom_lecture.pdf
- Oxfam. (2021). *The hunger virus multiplies: deadly recipe of conflict, covid19 and climate accelerate world hunger*. https://oi-files-d8-prod.s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/s3fs-public/2021-07/The%20Hunger%20Virus%20202.0_media%20brief_EN.pdf
- Raymond E. (1999). The cathedral and the bazaar. *Knowledge, Technology & Policy* 12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12130-999-1026-0>
- Rushkoff D. (2019). *Team Human*. WW Norton. <https://rushkoff.com/books/team-human-book/>
- TA Swiss, vdf Hochschulverlag AG, Bieri U, Braun Binder N, Salerno S, Keller T, Kälin M. (2021). *Where democracy and digitisation meet. Abridgement of the project «Democracy and digitisation»*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5187686>
- US Food and Drug Administration. (2013). *Mobile medical applications guidance for industry and Food and drug administration staff*. <https://www.federalregister.gov/documents/2013/09/25/2013-23293/mobile-medical-applications-guidance-for-industry-and-food-and-drug-administration-staff>
- US Food and Drug Administration. (2018). *Technical considerations for additive manufactured medical devices: guidance for industry and Food and Drug Administration staff*. <https://www.fda.gov/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/technical-considerations-additive-manufactured-medical-devices>
- US Food and Drug Administration. (2020). *Overview of Device Regulation*. <https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/device-advice-comprehensive-regulatory-assistance/overview-device-regulation>
- V-Dem Institute. (2021). *Autocratization Turns Viral. Democracy Report 2021*. <https://www.v-dem.net/files/25/DR+2021.pdf>
- van Dulmen S, Sluijs E, van Dijk L. et al. (2007). Patient adherence to medical treatment: a review of reviews. *BMC Health Services Research* 7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6963-7-55>
- Vercellone A. (2020). The italian experience of the commons: right to the city, private property, fundamental rights. *The Cardozo Electronic Law Bulletin*. <https://iris.unito.it/retrieve/handle/2318/1742871/620624/cardozo%20commons.pdf>
- Vergara C. (2020). *Systemic corruption: constitutional ideas for an anti-oligarchic republic*. Princeton University Press. <https://press.princeton.edu/books/hardcover/9780691207537/systemic-corruption>
- World Bank and World Health Organization. (2017). Half the world lacks access to essential health services, 100 million still pushed into extreme poverty because of health expenses. *World Health Organization*. <https://www.who.int/news/item/13-12-2017-world-bank-and-who-half-the-world-lacks-access-to-essential-health-services-100-million-still-pushed-into-extreme-poverty-because-of-health-expenses>
- World Health Organization. (2016). *Towards improving access to medical devices through local production. Report of a case study in four sub-Saharan countries*. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241510141>

Is the Digital Economy Market-Driven or Commons-Based?³

Lessons for the EU Digital Transformation Strategy

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1. Introduction

In 2006, Harvard Law School Professor Yochai Benkler published his seminal book *The Wealth of Networks: How Social Production Transforms Markets and Freedom*. In it, he documented an emerging phenomenon he named peer production, exemplified in projects like Wikipedia and free and open-source software (FOSS). In these projects, self-organised communities, with no pre-defined roles and structure, voluntarily contribute to content, information, and knowledge that is shared as digital commons. According to Benkler (2001; 2004; 2006), these projects demonstrated a mode of production and organisation fundamentally different and arguably more efficient from firms and markets, that would thereby dominate online content and information production.

Nicholas Carr, a technology and society author and former editor of the Harvard Business Review, critical of the Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) hype, challenged Benkler's positions in his blog⁴. Carr argued that it is only a matter of time until firms and formal managerial structures would find their ways in this new domain to reaffirm the efficiency of markets and drive of profits. Benkler commented on the blogpost reasserting his position and proposed a wager to measure his predictions' quality. Benkler argued that by 2011 the most influential websites would be based on content produced by people engaged in peer production. Carr maintained that the lure of money and the corporate hierarchies would be more effective. The Carr-Benkler wager, which was even reported in *The Guardian* (Arthur, 2006), triggered a debate in, at that time, bull blogosphere.

16 years later, with a digital economy pervading all spheres of human interaction, we revisit the Carr-Benkler wager. Is the digital economy peer-produced or market-driven?

2. Who won the bet?

In 2012, Carr revisited⁵ the wager and inferred that he had won. Carr pointed to the most influential websites across major categories of online activity that price-incentivized, commercial entities dominated. Benkler had predicted that peer production would be the dominant mode of online production, and Carr concluded that peer production had failed to realise that goal.

Benkler replied⁶ that peer production, a term he had introduced in 2002, referred to an emerging phenomenon that builds on the capacity for people to relate and connect over the Internet. This peer-to-peer capacity has given rise to projects that “capitalise on an enormous pool of underutilised intelligent human creativity and willingness to engage in intellectual effort” (Benkler, 2002: 30). From the unpaid user reviews of Amazon and the voluntary content creation on Facebook to the commons-based Wikipedia or the Free and Open Source Software (FOSS) projects, this peer-to-peer capacity had been utilised in different ways and with different political orientations (Kostakis, 2018; Bauwens et al., 2019). Therefore, for Benkler, peer producers were the ones who had been contributing a critical amount of value to the most influential websites. So, before we are able to decide who won the bet, we need to take a closer look into the contribution of peer production and the digital commons to the digital economy.

³ Based on Pazaitis, A., Kostakis, V. (2021) Are the most influential websites peer-produced or price-incentivized? Organizing value in the digital economy. *Organization*, 29(4): 757-769.

⁴ <https://www.rough.type.com/?p=466>

⁵ <https://www.rough.type.com/?p=1599>

⁶ <https://blogs.harvard.edu/ybenkler/2012/05/07/on-the-carr-benkler-wager/>

3. Not all peer production is the same

First, one should be aware of the subtle difference between peer production and commons-based peer production (CBPP). This difference between the two concepts, which are often used interchangeably, has become much more prominent in the last decade. Various forms of Internet-enabled socio-technical infrastructures can be identified, each of which may lead to different forms of social and political organisation (Kostakis and Bauwens, 2014). On one hand, consider the utilisation of peer production by Facebook, Google or Bitcoin. On the other hand, see the commons-oriented models of Wikipedia, FOSS and open design projects (Arvidsson, 2010; Giotitsas, 2019).

Let us compare two prominent platforms, namely Facebook and Wikipedia. Both are based on a layer of peer-to-peer communication, where users interact and share content and information. But in Facebook, this interaction is limited to the front-end of the platform that the users can access. In the back end, data is handled in a centralised manner, through opaque algorithms designed to maximise profits. Contrastingly, Wikipedia operates through transparent community rules and open source infrastructure. The control over content creation and allocation of relevance is distributed and is aimed at maximising its value for everyone.

Adopting a profit- or a commons-oriented socio-technical infrastructure and institutional design is the locus of social conflict because the choice between them qualifies some behaviours over others. Hence, peer production can be seen as a wider phenomenon from which CBPP emerges. Facebook, Google, or Amazon use peer production in fundamentally different ways to Wikipedia or the myriads of FOSS projects (e.g. Linux, Apache HTTP Server, Mozilla Firefox).

So, all peer production is not the same and socio-technical design matters in the digital economy. There is no definitive way to speak for one way of organisation or another.

4. The Internet is made by diverse contributions

Eghbal (2019) shows that not only the software behind the most influential websites, but also nearly all software used by Fortune 500 companies and governments is based on FOSS: from Apache, the most popular web server, to GNU/Linux, on which the top-500 supercomputers run, to WordPress, the most popular content management system, to OpenSSL, the most popular encryption protocol to secure transactions.

Although the majority of the influential websites seem to be run by commercial companies, a considerable part of their technological infrastructure is based on digital commons. But, one might ask, who is funding the digital commons communities? Indeed, Google, IBM, Facebook, Intel and Amazon have been supporting such communities. Even Microsoft, whose former CEO Steve Ballmer had said in 2001 that GNU/Linux is a “cancer,” has now been an ardent supporter of FOSS (Bright, 2019; Greene, 2001). However, the question should not be whether major tech companies are contributing directly or indirectly to FOSS but whether these companies are contributing enough and paying their fair share. It is also important to understand to what extent their contribution/support influences the direction of certain FOSS projects and how this impacts on the broader community of contributors and users.

Moreover, we have discussed above how Facebook and Wikipedia are both based on peer-produced content. However, platforms like Facebook manipulate the flow of information to boost types of interactions that are most relevant to their advertising clients. This extractive attitude diminishes the relevance of information to the platform’s users that co-produce it, destroying the social fabric that makes social media valuable in the first place. Even worse, it has been shown how it enables forms of exploitation to assert political influence, hate-speech or directly harm vulnerable user groups, as the recent cases of the “hate factory” (Knaus et al., 2019), Cambridge Analytica scandal (Wong, 2019), and Facebook Files ([Lima, 2001](#)) reveal.

Contrastingly, commons-based projects have exhibited a relatively high resilience to exploitation for self-interest. Wikipedia is the first result on many Google searches and has transparent accountability rules to flag and remove self-advertising contributions. Likewise, a recent study with the Debian community (O’Neil et al., 2021) demonstrates that, despite the increasing role of commercial entities in FOSS projects, like

paying developers' salaries, the impact on the contributors' working relations is considered insignificant. Conversely, livelihood opportunities offered by the financial support allow some less privileged contributors to work more on projects that interest them, thus strengthening the community ethics and potentially allowing more diversity. The impotence of the profit motive in CBPP reduces the impact of greed, while allowing more pluralistic forms of meaningful interaction and value creation, not accounted for in standard managerial practices, to become visible.

The infrastructure and content creation behind the most influential websites seems to be more commons-based than market-driven. However, both elements co-exist within an ever-changing environment. While financial incentives show to expose vulnerable groups, commons-based forms exhibit resilience by adapting commercial interests to the community rules, even when this struggle takes place in an unlevelled playing field, as we discuss in the next section.

5. There is no “natural” outcome in economy, technology or society

The turn of the digital economy towards its market-driven variation is seen by many as a “natural” economic development. But there is nothing really “natural” about the economy and market (Chang, 2010). All economic outcomes are essentially a result of political choices reified by the established institutional order. As Mazzucato (2013) shows, every technology that makes the iPhone a smartphone – Internet, GPS, touchscreen, battery, hard drive, voice recognition – was developed by researchers paid by the state. The same applies to Google's search algorithm. Moreover, publicly funded infrastructure, like the world wide web and the vast undersea cables network, make the digital economy possible to begin with. Public institutions regulate and oversee the conditions under which service providers can offer services, information is transmitted, and users access it. It is only after all the above are in place that competition and price-incentives can actually function.

Big tech exploits public-money-funded technologies and digital commons infrastructures by establishing opaque and proprietary business models to make huge profits. In addition, many of them systematically use loopholes in global tax rules to avoid giving back their fair share. Hence, the dominance of one modality over the other is a result of political definition. The state steers competition and profit-motives, implicitly rationalising the produced economic outcomes, in the way they are measured in the national accounts.

Alternately, there is no objective reason why the state cannot offer the same type of support it provided for big tech to digital commons communities (Bauwens et al., 2019; Pazaitis and Drechsler, 2020). For example, see how the city of Barcelona outsourced tech projects to local small and medium sized enterprises (Albers, 2018). With institutional and structural support the digital commons can create emancipatory spaces for alternative organisational forms that can increase democratic control and societal benefits in a vital domain.

Currently, our economic institutions largely assume that people are driven primarily by price signals, even though the larger part of human activity is, stubbornly, not price-incentivized. From our friends and family relations, to our work interaction beyond the strict terms of our job description to the broader social interaction in our neighbourhood, village or city. And so is our Internet-mediated social interaction. The Internet has enabled this productive sociality to happen at large scale. The digital commons is this particular domain where the qualities of social production are simply more visible.

6. Why is this important?

In this essay we attempt to make our case for the commons as a fundamental system of resources and relations underpinning the digital transformation. The commons have long been acknowledged as a vital domain for basic life support systems, heritage, traditions, and social systems. Likewise, the digital commons provide the basis upon which the digital economy has expanded.

The Carr-Benkler wager has been a starting point to examine the current social and political struggles in the process of digital transformation. It serves as a lens to unveil the adversary value systems underneath and the respective implications for organisation and public policy. Considering the EU strategy for “Europe's digital

decade” for 2030, we emphasise the contribution of the commons to the digital transformation, and how it is often taken for granted, becoming prone to exploitation and co-optation. On one hand, this tendency leads to the degradation of the commons upon which the digital transformation - and beyond - relies. On the other hand, it ignores viable commons-based alternatives that can improve democracy and sustainability in the process of the digital transformation. A truly sustainable and just deployment of digital technologies, for both society and the planet, needs to acknowledge and support the importance of the commons.

The task to measure the value of FOSS is quite challenging, yet a number of indications have been made. A 2009 study by Black Duck Software suggested that FOSS is cumulatively worth \$387 billion in savings (Asay, 2009). Tapscott and Williams (2006) estimate that IBM investments in Linux saves the company ca. \$1 billion annually from developing and maintaining proprietary software. A recent study (Blind et al., 2021) prepared for the European Commission showcase a substantial contribution of FOSS to the European Union’s economy, estimating that an increase of 10% in the number of FOSS commits, that is, individual changes in a software project, from 2017 to 2018 is translated into a 0.4% growth of the European Gross Domestic Product (GDP), which in 2018 terms was €63 billion per year. A marginal increase in the number of commits and contributors is expected to lead to an annual increase of the EU GDP of more than €100 billion. Nevertheless, there is not enough public data on the quantity and the quality of major tech companies’ contribution to FOSS development. Hence, one cannot have a clear idea about how much value the companies get from FOSS and how much value they reciprocate.

However, measuring how much website content is price-incentivized or peer-produced gets us already in the wrong direction. Any measurement is not neutral, and, in a market-driven economy, measure of value is only reflected in the exchange of one thing over another. But even if the market instrumentally validates the management of the interaction taking place in a platform, it does not necessarily determine the organisation of user affairs in the first place. A large part of Internet-mediated collaboration today has been, and continues to be organised autonomously, either between volunteers, or professionals, following peer-to-peer signalling and based on heterogeneous motivations.

An informed digital transformation strategy needs to understand how the digital commons are at the epicentre of this process. A non-exhaustive list of relevant policy measures are:

- Recognition of the contribution of digital commons by big tech and establishment of transparent rules for commercialisation and monetisation processes, with the participation of users and digital commons communities.
- Establishment of funding and support instruments for prominent digital commons projects and infrastructures, integrating participatory forms of governance and budgeting.
- Institutional support of commons-based licences and technological standards, including enforcement and litigation processes.
- Integration of open technology parks⁷ development in the digital transformation strategy.

In conclusion, who won the bet? Black or white questions like this reduce the possible answers to only two. However, the reality, as is often the case, is more complex. We saw that unpaid labor co-exists with paid labor, profit-maximization co-exists with commoning, and the homo economicus co-exists with the homo socialis. In 2006, Carr and Benkler had agreed that a dinner would be paid by the one who would lose the wager (Benkler, 2011: 191). Hence, it seems that Carr should pay for the main course while Benkler should pay for the dessert. Where we choose to place our own bets has to do with our vision and hopes for the future, as a dinner treat is the least we are bound to lose.

⁷ A list of initial proposals for open technology parks following a first round of public consultation in Greece can be found in the following link: <https://opentechpark.org/en/our-proposals>.

References

- Albers, E. (2018) ‘Using Free Software to Build A More Democratic, Inclusive and Sustainable Digital Society - Interview with Francesca Bria, CTO of Barcelona’, Free Software Foundation (edition) 5 July. Retrieved from <https://fsfe.org/news/2018/news-20180705-01.en.html> (Accessed: 30 June 2022).
- Arthur, C. (2006) ‘What is the Carr-Benkler wager?’, The Guardian (edition) 3 August. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2006/aug/03/guardianweeklytechnologysection> (Accessed: 30 June 2022).
- Arvidsson, A. (2010) ‘The Ethical Economy: New Forms of Value in the Information Society?’, *Organization* 17(5): 637–44.
- Asay, M. (2009) ‘Study: Open Source Worth \$387 Billion (In Savings)’, Cnet (edition) 15 April. Retrieved from <https://www.cnet.com/news/study-open-source-worth-387-billion-in-savings> (Accessed: 14 April 2020).
- Bauwens, M., Kostakis, V., Pazaitis, A. (2019) *Peer to Peer: The Commons Manifesto*. London: Westminster University Press.
- Benkler, Y. (2002) ‘Coase’s Penguin, or Linux and the Nature of the Firm’, *The Yale Law Journal* 112: 369–446.
- Benkler, Y. (2004) ‘Sharing Nicely: On Shareable Goods and the Emergence of Sharing as a Modality of Economic Production’, *The Yale Law Journal* 114(2): 273–358.
- Benkler, Y. (2006) *The Wealth of Networks: How Social Production Transforms Markets and Freedom*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- Benkler, Y. (2011) *The Penguin and the Leviathan: How Cooperation Triumphs Over Self-Interest*. New York, NY: Crown Business.
- Blind, K., Böhm, M., Grzegorzewska, P., Katz, A., Muto, S., Pätsch, S., Schubert, T. (2021). The impact of Open Source Software and Hardware on technological independence, competitiveness and innovation in the EU economy, Final Study Report. Brussels.
- Bright, P. (2019) ‘Microsoft: The Open Source Company’. *Arstechnica* (edition), 5 November. Retrieved from <https://arstechnica.com/gadgets/2019/05/microsoft-the-open-source-company> (Accessed: 30 June 2022).
- Chang, H.-J. (2010) *23 Things They Don’t Tell You About Capitalism*. London: Penguin Books.
- Eghbal, N. (2019) ‘Roads and Bridges: The Unseen Labor Behind Our Digital Infrastructure’, Ford Foundation. Retrieved from <https://www.fordfoundation.org/media/2976/roads-and-bridges-the-unseen-labor-behind-our-digital-in-frastructure.pdf> (Accessed: 30 June 2022).
- Giotitsas, C. (2019) *Open Source Agriculture: Grassroots Technology in the Digital Era*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Greene, C. T. (2001) ‘Ballmer: “Linux is A Cancer” Contaminates All Other Software with Hippie GPL Rubbish’, *The Register* (edition), 2 June. Retrieved from https://www.theregister.co.uk/2001/06/02/ballmer_linux_is_a_cancer (Accessed: 30 June 2022).
- Knaus, C., McGowan, M., Evershed, N., Holmes, O. (2019) ‘Inside the Hate Factory: How Facebook

Fuels Far-Right Profit'. The Guardian (edition), 5 December. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/australia-news/2019/dec/06/inside-the-hate-factory-how-facebook-fuels-far-right-profit> (Accessed: 30 June 2022).

- Kostakis, V. (2018) 'In Defense of Digital Commoning', *Organization* 25(6): 812–81.
- Kostakis, V., Bauwens, M. (2014) *Network Society and Future Scenarios for a Collaborative Economy*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Mazzucato, M. (2013) *The Entrepreneurial State: Debunking Public vs. Private Sector Myths*. London: Anthem Press.
- O'Neil, M., Muselli, L., Raissi, M., et al. (2021) 'Open Source Has Won and Lost the War': Legitimising Commercial–Communal Hybridisation in A FOSS Project,' *New Media & Society* 23(5): 1157–80.
- Pazaitis, A., Drechsler, W. (2020) 'Peer Production and State Theory: Envisioning a Cooperative Partner State', in O'Neil, M., Pentzold, C., Toupin, S. (eds) *The Handbook of Peer Production*, pp. 359–370. Hoboken, NJ: Wiley & Sons.
- Tapscott, D., Williams, A. (2006), *Wikinomics: How Mass Collaboration Changes Everything*. New York, NY: Portfolio.
- Wong, J. C. (2019) 'The Cambridge Analytica Scandal Changed the World – But It Didn't Change Facebook', The Guardian (edition), 18 March. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2019/mar/17/the-cambridge-analytica-scandal-changed-the-world-but-it-didnt-change-facebook> (Accessed: 30 June 2022).

SDGs and the commons: from a central missing topic towards recognition via national implementations?

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1. Commons really absent in SDGs?

The 17 SDGs are the major initiative of the United Nations (UN) to promote sustainable development implemented by states. But despite including comprehensively some of the globally pressing social issues such as poverty and justice, a closer look at the goals shows problematic omissions regarding other key social issues that are at least equally important for addressing some of the current environmental and development crises. Especially the commons, once perceived as a major issue in relation to sustainability and reflected by Elinor Ostrom's Nobel Prize, is completely left out. Ostrom's work was based on solid scientific evidence that local communities have often been able to establish institutional arrangements for the sustainable management of common-pool resources (pastures, wildlife, fisheries, forestry, water, etc.). While being directly linked to SDGs 14 and 15, the commons are relevant to all other SDGs (see e.g., hunger, energy, consumption, climate change and biodiversity loss). 'Commoning', as a process of shared governance, further relates much to SDGs 16 (peace, justice, and strong institutions) and 17 (participation).

2. How important are commons for SDGs and what are the specific policy needs?

Why are SDGs relevant for the debate on the commons in practice? First, the SDGs cover virtually all - social, economic, and environmental - arenas of action in a society, as this international framework brings together development and environmental issues and broadens them with the issues of achieving and sustaining improved justice and peace. Second, SDGs represent a serious global commitment in terms of its coverage, but also in terms of financial resources, as it is estimated that \$4.2 trillion per year - for comparison Germany's GDP is ca. \$3.8 trillion - shall be made available for the implementation of the SDGs (Joint SDG Fund 2022). At the same time, the SDGs provide political resources based on a hegemonic discourse that prescribes sustainable development through states and the private sector (Larsen, Haller and Kothari 2022). We show, on the one hand, while SDGs directly target commons-relevant resources and institutional arrangements on a mass scale, the dominant actors and discourse have not so far left much room to include the commons in the global debate on sustainability. On the other hand, we disentangle how and in what sense the commons were represented in pre-SDG frameworks and how they could be integrated into the SDGs going forward. Hence, we address two problematic issues due to the absence of the commons in SDGs. First, because common property regimes are not formally recognized in the SDGs, state elites can continue to legitimate commons grabbing. Second, leaving out the commons reduces local power claiming for participation. Thus, we also see two respective policy needs: a) ensuring that SDGs is not the abbreviation of «Sanctioning Disciplined Grabs» (see Larsen, Haller and Kothari 2022); and b) ensuring that local commoners (farmers, fishers, and nomads) can use and develop alternative and/or supplementary mechanisms to state-led and private-property-based governance during the implementation phases of SDGs.

3. How can we understand the term 'commons'?

A first glance at some previous international development and environmental policy frameworks show that the commons are often missing or only marginally integrated when we focus on local commons. This relates to debates on the definitions of the term 'commons'. In the academic debate before and after the seminal works of Ostrom (particularly, Ostrom 1990), the term 'commons' is defined broadly and analyzing what is understood by the term and how it relates to the SDGs can already shed some light on its early appearances and later disappearance. Our literature review reveals that numerous terms have been used between the 1980s - 2010s in the academic discourse: "Commons", "Governance of the Commons", "Common Property Resources", "Common Property Institutions", "Common Pool Resources", "Common Property Regimes", "open CPR", "closed CPR", "Resources held in common", "Commoner", "Commoning" (e.g., Berkes

2009; Sarker and Blomquist 2018; Quintana and Campbell 2019; Haller et al 2019; Cole 2020). In fact, the definitions and perceptions of the term have been interpreted so broadly that Sarker and Blomquist (2018) for example even talked about “Misconceptions of Commons”. Indeed, since Hardin’s (1968) article wrongly described the term commons, much has been dedicated to clarifying more accurate or theoretically sound ways of understanding the commons. If we go back to the main polemic misconception of Hardin, arguing that the commons is a property regime of resources based on an open access and must therefore lead to the collapse of the system due to overuse, while state and privatization are sustainable alternatives, the following insights are central.

Resources with specific qualities in terms of relatively low level of difficulty to exclude users from the resource system but with higher level of subtractability of the resource are to be understood as common-pool resources. These can be unmanaged (open access), controlled by the state or be privatized or be owned and managed as common property (including through membership and self-organized governance institutions) by local communities. While open access can lead to overuse, there is broad worldwide empirical evidence that governing the commons does not mean this is done via open access but rather through shared communal local property of common pool resources based on agreed upon local institutions (rules). Thus, a more nuanced understanding of the term ‘commons’ is one that recognizes these different aspects related to both a) characteristics of a shared resource system and b) presence of agreed upon shared governance arrangements. Ostrom concluded in her work that if local common property institutions are robust, they can be a promising avenue for sustainable use of natural resources. In fact, the empirical baseline for that discussion provided the foundation for Ostrom’s Nobel Prize. It represents an important contribution to the debate on sustainability. Such understanding of the commons enables us to examine if local commons as common property regimes are recognized in sustainability policies and not just as open-access or ambiguous ‘global’ commons.

4. How has the term commons been used in the sustainable development discourse?

Our discourse analysis identifies that the local commons is clearly missing in the pre-SDG frameworks such as the 1987 Brundtland Report ‘Our Common Future’, where commons were mentioned exclusively in the sense of global commons, while emphasizing their importance for the collective future. The report that provided the foundation for the discourse on sustainable development did not focus on the local collective governance of common-pool resources, which otherwise would also recognize local communal property rights and the right to establish rules and regulations. This becomes evident in the formulations such as “[...] ‘the global commons’ - those parts of the planet that fall outside national jurisdictions” (WCED 1987) with the examples of “oceans”, “outer space”, “Antarctica”. Some characteristics of the commons were then also rather superficially mentioned in the wording of “shared ecosystems” coupled with somewhat vague wording of “development of shared ecosystems” that uses the term “development” in relation to the term “ecosystems” without clarifying what this entails. In any case, the historically developed collective ownership and governance of sub-elements of these ecosystems was not addressed. Then, similar trends with some differences could be observed in the subsequent influential documents shaping the sustainable development agenda. For example, in the 2000 Millennium Development Goals – arguably the next most influential development agenda prior to the SDGs, there is still only very soft and only implicit references to commons characteristics as a shared resource system but with complete absence of recognition of common property regimes and local institutional arrangements. This becomes evident in formulations such as “ensure environmental sustainability”, “reverse the loss of environmental resources”, “reduce biodiversity loss”, all to some extent implicitly treated as systems with some shared value and that require collective action, but with no explicit mention of commons. Finally, in the 2015 SDGs, there is still very weak and only implicit references to the commons but this time with a stronger emphasis on the equality or equitability of sharing and ownership: “all men and women [...] have equal rights to economic resources”, “equal access to”, “ownership and control over land and...”. However, one could argue that this is even a fall-back for the commons discourse compared to the times of the Brundtland Report as the term ‘commons’ is not mentioned at all in the SDGs and there are no reflections on other governance forms apart from governing through state

and private sector. There is an impression with the SDGs that these are seen as the only forms of governance capable to reverse the social-environmental crises of our time.

5. What could explain the absence of commons in the SDGs?

How can we explain this puzzling absence of the commons from the SDGs despite the growing prominence of the commons discourse, particularly amplified through Ostrom's Nobel Prize, and a wide range of academic debates referring to the commons as a significant avenue for sustainability? One reason could be in the definitional challenges discussed above. The term 'commons' requires a nuanced understanding and although academic literature places a strong emphasis on this, policy and practice around sustainable development uses the term very scarcely, and if at all often implicitly and in very broad terms.

Another important explanation can be found in the lack of agency as states are seen as a default unit and agency in the making of SDGs and their implementation. Yet, this lack of agency of other than state and private sector actors exacerbates given the vested interests of the powerful actors creating plausible conditions for a more deliberate resistance towards the notion of commons due to prevailing perception of commons by governments and private actors as a 'complete' self-governance alternative to or even a rejection of state and privatization solutions. However, not only is this a well-established misconception (Sarker and Blomquist 2018), but it is also not known that Ostrom's view of the commons was driven by any such explicit political agenda, nor is it a reflection of how common property regimes have been related to private and state property historically or at present. In addition, external and internal power relations shaping the common property institutions were not at the centre of attention by the works of Ostrom (see Haller, Liechti and Mann 2021). However, despite the largely omitted power relations between private, state, and common property regimes in the commons discourse, the wrongly attributed anti-state connotation of the commons as potentially perceived by governments and some actors might explain to some extent why the commons are the great absent in the written documents dedicated to the SDGs.

Further aspect that can explain but also add to the puzzle of commons being left out of the SDGs is the omission of the literature since the 1980s which indicate that what is called 'nature' is actually the result of human landscape transformations. These were based on diversified extensive and intensive subsistence use (gathering, hunting, pastoralism and traditional agriculture) often based on pre-colonial communal resource regimes which created what can be called highly diverse 'cultural landscape ecosystems' all over the world (see Ellen 1982; Fairhead and Leach 1996; Haller 2019 a,b). If the SDGs are to protect 'nature', then it would be fair to claim that the immense diversity of cultural landscapes shall be protected. That would bring in the commons from another angle. This further adds to the puzzle of the normative perspectives related to the commons in the sense how and why various forms of common property regimes have evolved historically. But perhaps there is a power specific clue here: processes of resource encroachments, particularly on previously commonly owned lands, have not stopped with the end of colonisation. On the contrary, it has rather increased in developing countries, as a form of grabbing processes via privatization with the support of neo-liberal movements (Dell'Angelo et al. 2017; Giger et al 2019; Haller 2019, 2022).

Mentioning the commons could raise local claims to reverse that process (Larsen, Haller and Kothari 2022) and enable turning the 'drama of the grabbed commons' (Gerber and Haller 2021) into a process of land and resource recognition. It can be argued that this is partly why, despite an increasing involvement of NGOs in debates on sustainable development, commons have had a negative connotation from the perspectives of the governments and of powerful actors with vested interests. We can also observe that only since the middle of the last decade the term commons gained substantially more positive connotations. First this could be attributed to academic activists seeing commons as the process of communing an alternative way of sustainability (see Helferich and Bollier 2015) and later to neo-liberal movements, governments, as well as international development planners. How can this paradoxical shift be explained? There is sufficient evidence to assume that governments might have re-thought of commons as self-management not in the sense of giving back property rights and benefits but to reduce costs for the state – similar to the colonial form of indirect rule but without shared property rights provided and guaranteed (see also Schläppi 2018; Haller et al 2019).

However, the SDGs were written, shaped, and negotiated by states before this very recent period. Now the lack of the term ‘commons’ in SDGs has problematic repercussions as with that lack also related terms such as common-pool resources and common-property regimes and locally developed common property institutions are missing. The issue is that, as the commons are missing in the SDGs written documents, governments and the private sector are enabled even more than before to combine mainstream development and conservation programs and policies without truly involving local stakeholders with what might appear as ecologically sound justifications. It therefore not only does not provide a paradigm change towards sustainability but further worsens the status quo. The SDGs set a wider technocratic agenda that risks reproducing mainstream notions of development and nature from top down. It is not the local communities who have the definition power on what sustainability means as this still largely lies in the hands of the global north and to some extent in the hands of governments and powerful actors in the global south. There are many similarities here to older debates on development such as the Anti-Politics Machine that hide power asymmetries and state control behind notions of development for all (see Ferguson 1994). Now the SDGs are in danger to become a modern green anti-politics machine, hiding underlying power asymmetries by proposing a green development, while concealing who the polluters are and leaving out the majority of global actors. Phrases such as ‘leaving no one behind’ hides the structural processes that lead to leaving many behind. Instead, the formulations in the 17 goals and the sub-goals are written in a way that largely does not harm governments and ensures ‘leaving no governments behind’.

6. Five threats from the formal absence of commons in SDGs

We see five main threats that the SDGs pose for local commoners from an interdisciplinary social-environmental sciences perspective, but particularly from the perspective of new institutional political ecology (see Haller et al 2018; Haller 2019 a,b; Larsen, Haller and Kothari 2022):

- *Disregarding root causes of environmental destruction* and acting as a green Anti-Politics Machine helps to hide unequitable development and destructive power relations in interrelated global-local (‘glocal’) economies.
- *Mistreating cultural landscape ecosystems as «pure nature»*, which is a colonial view on locally managed cultural landscapes since the pre-colonial past, especially in the global south, helps legitimize discourse for green encroachments.
- The current formulations of the SDGs help *continue encroachments* as they enable the non-recognition of shared governance of common-pool resources, while hiding the dominance of state grabbing processes continued after colonial periods in the form of land grabbing as commons grabbing (land, pastures, wildlife, fisheries, forestry, water, etc., see Giger et al 2019 with reference to the land matrix).
- The lack of recognition towards commons in SDGs *undermines local participation* in defining new rules of sustainable governance, today largely directed by the state, private sectors, and state recognized NGOs. These actors are often not interested in self-defined local participation and participatory formulations of new goals & local institutions. It enables governments to enact control via the labelling of government driven processes of top-down participation as “commons” (see also the work of Fukuda-Parr 2019).
- The absence of commons in SDGs *increases options for powerful actors*, now provided with a well-supported environmental agenda, because the only participating actors are states, powerful environmental NGOs, and the private sector (multinational companies). This increases the danger that the SDGs are leading to more commons grabbing through for example Private Public Partnerships (PPP) legitimized by the narratives of poverty reduction and sustainable development to be used to remove property rights from local commoners often also in the context of conservation areas and green

energy development projects (biofuel, solar, and wind energy). In such projects companies can justify activities by developing Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) schemes related to the SDGs and hiding exploitative labour relations (Gerber and Haller 2021). Furthermore, governments are enabled to replace genuine participation with top down participation and processes of silencing critique via incorporation of key terms. Talking about justice without meaning redistribution and about partnership while hiding polluters are strategies that become visible. The problem is that the SDGs fit well into the notion of a neo-colonial and neoliberal global governance system.

These five critical observations (see also Larsen, Haller and Kothari 2022) can be illustrated at least in the following six global action arenas, where accumulation of wealth by some through dispossession of others becomes easier with the SDGs:

- *Agro-industrial sectors* (land grabbing, deforestation – palm oil industries)
- *Mining* for electric & climate smart cars (relates to SDGs on green energy and climate change)
- *Forests conservation* (Half Earth and 30 x 30 agendas) – conservation relates to life on land and water
- *Top down development schemes* (e.g., conservation agriculture, aquaculture, etc.) related to sustainable energy (7) and infrastructure (9) and the range of SDGs related to hunger and development (from SDG 1 to 3)
- *Mega-Infrastructure* becomes sustainable, hiding commons grabbing (pasture, fisheries, wildlife, local agricultural lands, access to water)
- *Hegemonic territorial framing*: land use planning for continued grabbing based on a process of territorialisation and increasing state control.

Last but not least, the SDGs can not only legitimize commons and resilience grabbing processes based on a neoliberal green agenda, but also turn the legitimacy and incorporation of the critique into productive discursive assets in order to accumulate more capital. Options for these can be tax policies with reference to the SDGs, the use of further regional development banks and other funds (such as on the EU or on Inter-African or -American levels) and finally the Global Funds for Sustainable Development.

7. What are the potential strategies for (policy) action?

What are now policy options, which we can observe and continue discussing in the context of this rather negative outline? While SDGs are written, they cannot be rewritten at the moment (but see experiment results of rewriting the SDGs; see Haller et al 2018), which leads us to propose two actions in policy arena:

Strategy I: Documentation of commons grabbing via SDGs and establishment of a centralized globally nested body of control (ombudsperson position). Further research and documentation is needed to show how the use of SDGs enable and legitimize commons grabbing processes by states and private sector (already documented examples are in Kenya: LAPPSET corridor in Kenya referring to the SDGs and Agenda 2030 and thus legitimizing the undermining of fisheries and nomadic pastoralism (Werthmüller in press) and conservation projects such as LEWA illustrated as a role model for participation, while in fact representing a form of green commons grabbing (see Weissman 2019). These documentations shall be used to create the basis for policy change that can be demanded by the commoners. Furthermore, it helps to legitimize local resistance and file legal actions. Similar to the land matrix for land grabbing, we could think of a matrix of commons grabbing via SDGs.

Strategy II: Activating Policy Opportunities. An example from Switzerland with a first-hand experience is useful here. In Switzerland, local commoner's organisations in collaboration with researchers form history, geography, social anthropology departments of the University of Bern have been trying to "sneak" into the implementation process of national SDGs by making use of state policy strategy that is responsible for implementing the SDGs on the national level. Researchers from the University of Bern (Lead Institute of

Social Anthropology, T. Haller) show in a project funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (Project Sustainable Commons Adaptations to Landscape Ecosystems in Switzerland (SCALES, see Haller, Liechti and Mann 2021) the vital role of the commons for the maintenance of Swiss cultural landscape ecosystems. Between 30 to 90% of all alpine pastures and forests in different cantons in Switzerland are in collective ownership of commoner's organisations. There is a great variation between cantons but overall this counts for at least 30% of all forests and alpine pastures in the country. Compared to the commons grabbing situations that commoners are facing in the global south, the Swiss commons are relatively well protected. However, their situation is still fragile as Swiss commoners have to balance between low market prices for their products (agrarian dairy products and timber) and top down planning of subsidies by the state which does not cover commoner's costs for maintaining the cultural landscapes. It depends on their respective bargaining power related to municipalities, cantons (districts) and the Federal Government as well as on their economic strategies. Research has shown that innovations helping them to maintain and internally cross-subsidize market specific parts of their property, which produce a deficit, increase this bargaining power. This means that income from real estates is used to cover deficits from forestry and alpine pasture use. This also helps the commoners' organisations to adhere to their sustainability aims to be able to use their properties not for short-term monetary profit but for future generations. Their value calculation is not just market-oriented but rather oriented towards an identity utility in the form of maintaining the cultural landscape heritage. In addition, commoners' organisations are aware of the critique of exclusion of other users and experiment with inclusionary internal policies as well as addressing the problematic gender imbalance in their organisations inherited from the past (see Haller et al 2021). Commoners' organisations are now trying to sensitize the public but especially policy makers and administrators that the commoners are to be recognized in the national implementation phase of the SDGs. More specifically, it is the aim to get the commoners recognized in the written Swiss national SDGs reports to the UN as partners and negotiate binding rules of participatory collaboration between the state and the commoners organisations related to the national SDGs implementation. This might be a first step into having a first case of a country that recognizes common property regimes of common pool resources and its relevance for the SDGs. It is hoped that the reference to the Swiss governmental recognition could help commoners' organisations and movements in other countries (especially by local and indigenous communities) to claim the same form of recognition.

Overall, despite the historical promise of the commons discourse that appears to have influenced the early sustainable development agenda, our closer analysis unfortunately reveals rather negative trends. Not only the commons have slowly disappeared from the formulations related to the global sustainability agenda, but the latest framework in the form of powerful SDGs also provide an easier platform for destruction and grabbing of the commons. We need to understand and document these processes better and activate policy opportunities to bring the much-needed value of the commons back into the SDGs in ways that can prevent or reverse these processes.

References

- Berkes, F. (2009). Evolution of co-management: role of knowledge generation, bridging organizations and social learning. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 90(5), 1692-1702.
- Cole, D.H. (2020). Elinor Ostrom, Pioneer of the Commons (and Much More). In Laitos, Jan G. and John Copeland Nagle, eds. *Pioneers of Environmental Law*. Twelve Tables Press. pp. 151-172.
- Ellen, R. (1982). *Environment, Subsistence and System. The ecology of small-scale social formations*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Fairhead, J. and Leach, M. (1996). *Misreading the African Landscape: Society and Ecology in a Forest-Savanna Mosaic* (Vol. 90). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Fukuda-Parr, S. (2019). Keeping out extreme inequality from the SDG Agenda—the politics of indicators. *Global Policy*, 10, 61–69.

- Gerber, JD and Haller, T. (2021). The drama of the grabbed commons: anti-politics machine and local responses. *The Journal of Peasant Studies*, 48(6), 1304–1327, DOI: [10.1080/03066150.2020.1758673](https://doi.org/10.1080/03066150.2020.1758673).
- Giger, M., Nolte, K., Anseuw, W., Breu, T., Messerli, P., Oberlack, C., and Haller, T. (2019). Impacts of large-scale land acquisitions on common-pool resources: evidence from the land matrix. In: Haller, T., Breu, T., de Moor, T., Rohr, C., Znoj, H. (eds.) *The Commons in a Glocal World: Global Connections and Local Responses*. London: Routledge. pp. 257–279.
- Dell’Angelo, J, D’Odorico, P., Rulli, M. C. and Marchand, P. (2017). The tragedy of the grabbed commons: coercion and dispossession in the global land rush. *World Development*, 92, 1–12.
- Haller, T. *et al.* (2018). Paradigm Change or Old Wine in New Bottles? Debating and Reformulating SDGs – An Experiment. Institute of Social Anthropology, University of Bern. http://www.anthro.unibe.ch/unibe/portal/fak_historisch/dkk/anthro/content/e40416/e96353/e96354/files747906/SDG_Text_Final_ger.pdf
- Haller, T. (2019). Towards a new institutional political ecology: how to marry external effects, institutional change and the role of power and ideology in commons studies, in: Haller, T. Breu, T., de Moor, T. Rohr, C., Znoj, H. (eds.). *The Commons in a Glocal World: Global Connections and Local Responses*. London: Routledge. pp 90-120.
- Haller, T. (2019b). The Different Meanings of Land in the Age of Neoliberalism: Theoretical Reflections on Commons and Resilience Grabbing from a Social Anthropological Perspective. *Land*, 8(7), 104. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land8070104>
- Haller, T., Breu, T., de Moor, T., Rohr, C., and Znoj, H. (eds.). (2019). *The Commons in a Glocal World: Global Connections and Local Responses*. Routledge: London.
- Haller, T., Liechti, K., Mann, S. (2021). Commons and peasant studies: Insights from social anthropology, human geography and agrarian economics. In Haller, T, Liechti, K., Stuber, M., Viallon, FX., and Wunderli, R. (eds). *Balancing the Commons in Switzerland. Institutional Transformations and Sustainable Innovations*. Routledge. London. Pp.45-60.
- Haller, T. (2022). From commons to resilience grabbing: Insights from historically-oriented social anthropological research on African peasants. *Continuity and Change*, 37(1), 69-95.
- Hardin, G. (1968). The Tragedy of the Commons. *Science*, New Series, Vol. 162, No. 3859, pp. 1243-1248. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1724745>
- Helfrich, S., & Bollier, D. (2015). *Die Welt der Commons: Muster gemeinsamen Handelns* (p. 384). Transcript Verlag.
- Joint SDG Fund (2022). Innovative mechanism of the United Nations. URL: <https://www.jointsdgfund.org/sdg-financing#:~:text=The%20Joint%20SDG%20Fund%20is,clear%20path%20to%20self%2Dsufficiency.>
- Larsen, P. B., Haller, T., & Kothari, A. (2022). Sanctioning Disciplined Grabs (SDGs): From SDGs as Green Anti-Politics Machine to Radical Alternatives? *Geoforum*, 131, 20-26.
- Ostrom, E. (1990). *Governing the Commons*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Quintana, A., & Campbell, L. M. (2019). Critical commons scholarship: A typology. *International Journal of the Commons*, 13(2).

- Sarker, A., & Blomquist, W. (2019). Addressing misperceptions of governing the commons. *Journal of Institutional Economics*, 15(2), 281-301.
- Schläppi, D. 2018. Einleitung. In: *Von der Allmende zur Share Economy. Gemeinbesitz und kollektive Ressourcen in historischer und rechtlicher Perspektive*, edited by D. Schläppi and M.-C. Gruber. Berlin: Berliner Wissenschaftsverlag, pp. 9-70.
- WCED (1987). Our common future. *Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development*.
- Weissman, S. (2019). Discourse and entanglement in a transnational conservation arena: Deciphering the ideologies and narratives behind conservation discourse in the ‘glocal’ commons in Kenya. in Haller, T. Breu, T., de Moor, T. Rohr, C., Znoj, H. (eds.). *The Commons in a Glocal World: Global Connections and Local Responses*. London: Routledge. pp. 392-413.
- Werthmüller, F. in press. Fishing in Troubled Waters: the impacts of LAPSSSET on the local fisheries in Lamu, Kenya, in Haller, T, and Weissman, S. (eds.). in press. *Disenchanted Modernities: Mega-Infrastructure Projects, Socio-Ecological Changes and Local Responses*.